

MARINEWIND

Market Uptake Measures of Floating Offshore Wind Technology Systems (FOWTs)

1/11/2022 – 31/10/2025

Call: HORIZON-CL5-2021-D3-02

Project 101075572 — MARINEWIND

D3.2: Analysis of technological barriers and enablers of floating offshore wind

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Submission date: 30/04/2024

Dissemination level		
PU	Public, fully open	x
SEN	Sensitive, limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement	

Document history

Issue Date	Version	Changes made / Reason for this issue
26/05/2023	0.1	Working draft shared with consortium
10/07/2023	0.2	Advanced draft shared with consortium + summary table listing thematic barriers and enablers.
22/11/2023	0.3	Draft shared for comments
08/02/2024	0.4	Hybrid systems addition (RSE & ESC)
15/02/2024	0.5	Restructure Structure and Content (CNR-RSE- ESC.)
08/04/2024	0.6	Final Draft
21/04/2024	0.8	Final Draft for Tech QA review
24/04/2024	0.9	First revision UoY
28/04/2024	10.0	Final revision UoY and APRE

Funded by the European Union. However, views and opinions expressed are those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

TABLE OF CONTENTS.....	3
TABLE OF FIGURES.....	5
LIST OF TABLES	6
EXECUTIVE SUMMARY.....	7
1. INTRODUCTION	12
2. TECHNOLOGICAL BARRIERS AND ENABLERS.....	16
2.1. HIGH COSTS.....	16
2.2. GRID CONNECTION AND POWER TRANSMISSION.....	16
2.3. DESIGN, OPERATIONS, MAINTENANCE, AND DECOMMISSIONING	19
2.4. SUPPLY CHAIN AND MANUFACTURING	28
2.5. RELIABILITY AND DURABILITY.....	32
2.6. ONGOING RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT	34
2.7. STANDARDISATION, COMPLIANCE AND CERTIFICATION	40
2.8. ELECTRICITY NETWORKS, GRID CONNECTIVITY AND FLEXIBILITY	40
2.9. NON-TECHNOLOGICAL BARRIERS AND ENABLERS.....	42
2.9.1. REGULATORY AND PERMITTING CHALLENGES	42
2.9.2. ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT	43
2.9.3. PUBLIC ACCEPTANCE	44
2.9.4. SUPPORTING MARKET SIGNALS, REGULATIONS, AND SYSTEMS COORDINATION.....	45
2.10. SUMMARY OF KEY ENABLERS.....	45
2.10.1. TECHNOLOGICAL ENABLERS	45
2.10.2. FINANCIAL ENABLERS:.....	46
2.10.3. ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACTS.....	47
2.10.4. REGULATORY AND PERMITTING	47
3. SYSTEMS INTEGRATION BARRIERS AND ENABLERS	48
3.1. CHARACTERISTICS OF FLOATING OFFSHORE WIND FARMS	58
3.1.1. FOCUS ON ITALY	59
3.2. GRID INTEGRATION AND FLEXIBILITY	62
3.3. HYBRID SYSTEMS	65
3.3.1. WAVE ENERGY: STATE OF THE ART AND MARKET ANALYSIS.....	68
3.3.2. TIDAL CURRENT ENERGY: STATE OF THE ART AND MARKET ANALYSIS.....	70
3.3.3. OFFSHORE FLOATING PHOTOVOLTAIC: STATE OF THE ART AND MARKET ANALYSIS.....	72

3.3.4. CASE STUDIES	74
3.4. STORAGE SYSTEMS	74
3.4.1. ONGOING RESEARCH AND INNOVATIONS	75
<u>4. CONCLUSIONS</u>	<u>81</u>
<u>5. REFERENCES</u>	<u>82</u>
<u>6. ANNEX.....</u>	<u>92</u>
6.1. WIND WAVE AND SOLAR (SARDINIA - IT) POTENTIAL PRODUCTION SMOOTHING	92
6.2. WIND AND SOLAR (RAVENNA -IT) INCREASE OF PRODUCTION IN A GIVEN AREA	98
6.3. WIND AND SOLAR (SICILY - IT) ECONOMIC ANALYSIS FOR ELECTRICAL INFRASTRUCTURE SHARING	101
6.4. WIND AND HYDROGEN PRODUCTION (LAZIO - IT) TECHNO-ECONOMIC ANALYSIS	105

TABLE OF FIGURES

Figure 1: Offshore wind global ambitions (Floating wind farms indicated with a blue icon) [6]	13
Figure 2: Platform design types for floating offshore wind [14].....	22
Figure 3: Mean annual wind speed @ 100 m a.g.l./a.s.l. [55]	60
Figure 4: The regional distribution (%) of the cumulative on-land wind energy installed capacity in 2023 (left) and the Italian region map (right).	61
Figure 5: Expected trend of RES installed capacity (TWh) increase to meet Italian NECP 2030 targets [56].	61
Figure 6: Map of new RES grid connection requests as of 31st December 2023 (source TERNA [57]): PV plants are yellow, onshore wind plants are green, and offshore wind plants are blue.	62
Figure 7 Tyrrhenian link (source TERNA[58])......	62
Figure 8 Approximate timeframes of different balancing services [61]......	64
Figure 9: Main Feature of storage technologies (Wikipedia).	64
Figure 10: Total wind curtailment by month, GB, and Scotland.....	66
Figure 11: Conceptual design of the floating hybrid wind-wave platform system [71].	67
Figure 12: Co-location of floating wind and wave farm (Source Mocean Energy/Illustration – Wave Energy Scotland [72])......	67
Figure 13: An overview of WECs [73]......	68
Figure 14: LCOE of 1GW Wind-Wave Farm with increasing WEC Capacity Factor (CF) [79].	70
Figure 15: Artist’s impression of co-located wind and wave farm.	70
Figure 16: Tidal stream turbine design[84]......	71
Figure 17: Floating PV farm (73 kWp) On a lake in the Netherlands [90]......	72
Figure 18: Nearshore floating PV farm (5 MWp) in Singapore[91]......	73
Figure 19: Offshore floating PV farm: artistic visualisation[93]......	73
Figure 20: Co-location of offshore floating PV and wind farm: artistic visualisation[97]......	74
Figure 21: Specific trend of normalised power generated by each device over the TMY.....	93
Figure 22: Trend of normalised power generated by the hybrid system over the TMY.	94
Figure 23: The trend of the normalised power generated by the hybrid system is one week during each of the four seasons during the TMY.....	95
Figure 24: Layout of the conceptual offshore Hybrid System: photovoltaic platforms (Grey) + Wind turbines (Red).	98
Figure 25 – Trend of winter power generation from the offshore wind and photovoltaic park.....	100
Figure 26 - Trend of summer power generation from the offshore wind and photovoltaic park.....	100
Figure 27 - Shadows cast by the turbines obscure the photovoltaic modules installed within the wind farm.	101
Figure 28 - Solar Paths are considered Sites in the Sicily Channel.....	102
Figure 29 – Annual power generation from the offshore photovoltaic park (Red) and power loss due to shading of the modules caused by the shadow cast by the turbines (Green).	103
Figure 30 - Results of an economic analysis for the case study of a hybrid system considered installed in the Sicily Channel.....	104

Figure 31: LCOH variation with respect to the cost of the energy supplying the electrolyser in three different cases..... 105

Figure 32: Connection options considered with two configurations 108

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1: Pros and Cons of Floating offshore wind platform design types 22

Table 2: Installation considerations for different floating design types..... 26

Table 3: Specific access issues by floating design types 27

Table 4: A review of marine renewable energy storage [102] 77

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Shifting from high-carbon energy sources to low-carbon technologies is crucial for achieving net-zero emissions. The growth of offshore wind, particularly floating wind, represents a significant step forward in this transition and is gaining increasing attention each year. Globally, 227 megawatts (MW) of floating offshore wind capacity are fully operational, spread across 14 projects in 7 countries; 46 MW of floating offshore wind capacity is currently under construction; with 76 MW of floating offshore wind capacity consented or in the pre-construction phase, across 11 projects. In terms of projects in the pipeline and early development, 68 gigawatts (GW) of floating offshore wind capacity are currently in the planning phase or have a lease agreement across 80 projects, and 175 GW of floating offshore wind capacity are in early development or applying for a lease, across 177 projects. From a regional breakdown, nearly two-thirds of the planned and developing floating offshore wind capacity (160GW) is being developed in European waters. 14% of the global floating offshore wind capacity (35 GW) is being developed in UK waters, with 29 GW of that in Scottish waters [1]

Despite challenges such as increasing costs, regulatory hurdles, uncertain policies, limited infrastructure, technology concerns, extended lead times, and the need to boost productivity, the industry is gearing up for a surge in demand towards the end of the decade. This surge is expected to exceed the current global capacity to achieve the Net Zero targets. In the latter part of this decade, plans are underway to install turbines exceeding 15 MW on floating platforms, with the subsequent deployment of around 20 MW turbines in the 2030s [2] [3].

Floating offshore wind presents a promising solution to address the challenges of climate change and energy deficits. However, realising its full potential requires establishing a global industry through strategic investments in innovative technologies, infrastructure, and supply chains. Key enablers for the growth of floating offshore wind include:

Competitive market framework: Governments can support the development of floating offshore wind farms by providing financial incentives and implementing policies and regulations that reduce risks and shape the industry. This competitive market framework is crucial to stimulate technological investment. [4].

Innovation in emerging technologies and standardisation: Advancement in floating foundation designs (aided by advanced integrated design tools), installation methods, and wind turbine technologies tailored for offshore applications are critical, especially for harsh environments (e.g., the Med Sea). Standardising key components (moorings, floater, wind turbine, control systems) can also help reduce design, production, and deployment costs. Investment in farm control systems to enhance global productivity is deemed important.

Enhancing the Supply Chain: Building a robust and efficient supply chain capable of delivering components and services at scale is essential. This can create jobs and economic opportunities in coastal communities while ensuring early commitment to port infrastructure and emphasising social value aspects like skills development and environmental protection.

Strategic partnerships: Collaboration between experienced industrial players and local stakeholders can leverage expertise and resources to drive innovation, reduce costs and improve data sharing. Partnerships between the industry and the scientific community are fundamental to accelerating innovations' demonstration and validation. The several research Tasks of the International Energy Agency Wind Technology Collaboration Programme demonstrate this. [5].

Grid reinforcement: To tap into new geographic regions and reward markets, grid infrastructure must be enhanced and reinforced to be fit for the 2030s and beyond. This will require enhancing grid infrastructure to support a large volume of renewable generation. This will help drive market growth, increase economies of scale, and accommodate more generated wind energy and storage.

This document explores the technological barriers and opportunities for advancing floating offshore wind, focusing on the six partner countries of the MARINEWIND project. It provides an in-depth analysis of the current state of Floating Offshore Wind Technology (FOWT) and the factors that can facilitate or hinder investment and deployment. The findings and priorities identified in the document aim to guide policymakers, industry stakeholders, and researchers in accelerating the adoption of FOWTs in these regions.

Key findings and priorities

Competitive Market Framework

A robust government strategy is essential to ensure energy security and facilitate the formulation of effective implementation plans. The expansion of floating wind in the market hinges on political backing in pivotal regions. With adequate support, its use may be unrestricted to specialised uses and face challenges competing with established technologies in auctions. Yet, with strong political backing and well-defined market strategies, there is potential for widespread adoption, paving the way for substantial economic growth and benefits at both local and regional levels.

A policy and regulatory framework are required to catalyse the market. Essential policy support is vital for advancing the floating offshore wind market. This involves implementing tailored standards, certifications, and reform policies to facilitate commercialisation and industrialisation. It also includes identifying opportunities to influence international standards and codes for global market impact. The scale and location of future deployments depend on supportive regional policies, regulations, and industry innovation.

Strategic partnerships can drive collaboration and joint investments in infrastructure. The Private and public sectors can foster partnerships with major industries, such as manufacturing, to support local industries by developing specialised skills, tools, and job creation.

A whole system approach is required for integrating floating wind into the energy system, involving innovation roadmaps and systematic development to analyse the compatibilities of technologies within energy systems. Additionally, it requires their seamless integration into a network of progressively intricate and interconnected energy systems. Additionally, the short-term evolution and long-term vision of the CfD scheme are essential. These efforts aim to advance decarbonisation, flexibility, and system integration and alleviate the effects of market distortion. It is also necessary to consider out-of-market mechanisms for essential backup plants to ensure the security of the energy supply.

Non-price criteria for floating offshore wind projects should be incentivised in auctions. This includes acknowledging and rewarding low embodied carbon designs and ensuring local communities have a stake in the development process. Implementing clear actions to address and reduce environmental concerns should be a priority, and adherence to the circular economy should be emphasised.

Innovation in Emerging Technologies

Enhanced Research and Development initiatives to address the engineering complexities linked to integrating floating offshore wind components. The 6 degrees of freedom exhibited by floating offshore wind turbines bring complexities in how turbine components interact and interface with the substructure. Tackling this challenge requires a multidisciplinary approach leveraging state-of-the-art tools. To achieve this, gathering knowledge and data for a more comprehensive understanding of the complex physical phenomena governing the engineering interface of offshore wind turbines can be facilitated through pilot projects and collaborative initiatives between manufacturers, developers, and the scientific community.

Optimisation of platform and wind turbine design is necessary to improve the durability of floating offshore wind farms. Floating platforms have been developed to mitigate rotational movements and displacements. However, it is necessary to establish industry standards and increase the technical readiness levels (TRLs) for different platform types to determine their applicability. Furthermore, sea basin-tailored designs for the floater and the turbine are needed to deal with environmental conditions encountered at offshore locations. This standardisation ensures floating offshore wind farms' long-term reliability and performance.

Floating offshore wind requires a dynamic electrical infrastructure, including dynamic cables, specialised connectors, protectors, and additional ancillary equipment. Unlike the existing offshore electrical infrastructure employed in bottom-fixed wind and the oil and gas industries, which lack these components and have established Technology Readiness Levels (TRLs), such elements are essential for floating offshore wind projects. They serve as potential single points of failure for individual turbines in the event of faults in the inter-array cabling. Moreover, they play a critical role in the overall wind farm, particularly in the case of export cable (i.e. those transferring the electrical power from offshore to onshore) failures.

Advanced mooring, anchoring, and stationkeeping solutions are essential for the floating platform, addressing the challenges posed by large amplitude motions and varying loading conditions that require adaptable equipment. Effective stationkeeping protects the site's electrical infrastructure from potential damage. Incorporating cutting-edge technologies and unconventional materials in mooring systems, such as mooring springs, dampeners, synthetic mooring lines, and innovative anchoring systems like mechanical anchors, can extend the system's lifespan, mitigate tension fatigue and contribute to cost reduction.

Dedicated vessels are essential for installing and servicing floating offshore wind turbines. Research and development efforts are crucial for enhancing these specialised vessels to improve the transportation and installation of fully assembled wind turbines and platforms. Developing specialised vehicles is also key to enabling on-site maintenance of wind turbines, minimising downtime, decreasing reliance on towing, and alleviating congestion at ports.

Robustness of Supply Chain

A systematic approach to developing the supply chain for floating offshore wind requires coordinated efforts across international standards, local supply chain investment, and supporting infrastructure. Addressing these elements holistically is key to driving this renewable energy technology's successful commercialisation and industrialisation. These efforts must be done in collaboration and require coordination across national

boundaries. In addition, enabling investment in the local supply chain is a key driver for creating advanced materials, manufacturing methods, and components needed for floating offshore wind.

Integrating Port Infrastructure and Grid Reinforcement: When considering the supply chain for floating offshore wind, it is crucial to account for the essential port infrastructure and grid reinforcement needed to facilitate the installation and operation of these systems. Integrating these broader infrastructure components into the overall supply chain strategy is vital as the crucial link between maritime developments and onshore operations. Their strategic location presents an opportunity to transform them into versatile hubs for offshore wind projects, alleviating both local and global supply chain limitations. Beyond traditional logistical functions, ports can evolve into centres for manufacturing and assembly, distribution points for specialised components, and providers of skilled labour and support services specific to floating offshore wind technologies.

Standardisation and modularity of components will increase supply chain resilience and ease global supply chain saturation. Introducing standards for components will lower the complexity of designs and enable their mass production, resulting in faster build and deployment rates and increasing the industry's maturity. Moreover, standardisation will enable the floating offshore wind supply chain to achieve economies of scale, thus reducing the levelised cost of energy.

Enhancing the installation process, optimising operations, and scheduling predictive maintenance will strengthen the robustness of the floating wind supply chain. This involves streamlining installation processes, implementing operational efficiencies, and adopting predictive maintenance practices, leading to increased reliability, minimised downtime, and improved cost-effectiveness. The key to this approach includes strategies for lifespan extension, minimising emergency repairs through predictive maintenance, and ensuring seamless wet and dry connectivity. Cutting-edge continuous monitoring systems, leveraging technologies such as remote sensing and autonomous drones, play a crucial role in reducing the costs associated with on-site system integrity monitoring. Using SCADA data and maintenance schedules, coupled with a network of service contractors, further strengthens the floating wind supply chain's overall resilience and commercial viability and supports the offshore wind industry's broader adoption and success.

Strategic Partnership through Digitalisation, Collaboration, and Knowledge Sharing

Promoting collaboration and data sharing between developers will accelerate the advancement of floating wind innovation. While engineering solutions for technical challenges already exist, optimising these designs relies on efficient feedback loops and mechanisms for sharing data. The improvement of existing designs can be achieved through a shared knowledge interface between projects, though implementing such collaboration may necessitate financial incentivisation guided by policies.

Promoting collaboration between the industry and the scientific community will facilitate tailored innovations. The efforts of several EU-funded projects and the IEA WIND Tasks demonstrate the crucial role of a strong partnership between these two sectors in advancing innovation within the industry. This partnership is essential for overcoming critical technological limitations and developing beyond state-of-the-art tools. In pursuit of this goal, it is imperative to prioritise two-way knowledge and data sharing as research studies rely on assessment data. At the same time, developing next generation floating offshore wind systems requires more advanced integrated tools for design and operation.

Early engagements with infrastructure providers and the scientific and local community will accelerate the rate of wind farm deployment. Environmental Impact Assessments (EIA) may occasionally impede project advancements, underscoring the importance of early engagement with the scientific community to leverage their

expertise in reducing environmental impact, including strategic planning of cable routes. Likewise, engaging local communities from the outset of the approval process and sustaining open communication throughout the project can alleviate resistance to developments. Consultation with ports during the preliminary planning phases facilitates a holistic approach encompassing manufacturing, assembly, transportation, and maintenance considerations.

Continued support for in-situ research and pilot projects remains crucial for gaining insights that extend beyond the capabilities of numerical modelling simulations or lab-scale experiments. The scale and intricacy of floating offshore wind structures, the complexities of the broader marine ecosystem, and limited historical data present challenges in accurately modelling certain design aspects or replicating them at a reduced scale in laboratory environments. Moreover, the detailed data obtained from pilot projects plays a fundamental role in advancing more advanced numerical tools, eventually leveraging Machine Learning techniques to develop digital twins of wind farms. Providing financial support for pilot projects is essential in bridging this knowledge gap and fostering the development of effective solutions.

Integrated numerical modelling and multi-body hydrodynamic analysis offer additional insights that complement those obtained from operational scenarios. These models can simulate extreme stresses on the system, revealing information not present in the dataset—specifically, extremes in environmental conditions induced by severe weather.

Integrating digitalisation, artificial intelligence (AI), and machine learning is poised to drive cost reductions throughout the sector. Digital twin technology facilitates the collection, visualisation, and analysis of data about the floating structure and the wind farm across its entire lifecycle—from design to decommissioning. This technology can be applied at the turbine level to optimise designs, minimise weight, and lower costs. Additionally, it enables real-time monitoring and predictive maintenance, ultimately reducing installation and operational expenses.

Grid Reinforcement

Considerable focus must be placed upon realising the Holistic Network Design and a grid system fit for the 2030s and beyond. Achieving this goal requires substantial investments in electrical infrastructure and significant policy changes to facilitate the successful implementation of a new vision for holistic and coordinated network design. The diverse connection regimes (radial, offshore non-radial, transmission operator, interconnector) may create an uneven playing field among projects without the implementation of appropriate policies. While this transformation will take time, developers require prompt certainty to ensure timely procurement of long-lead electrical infrastructure items.

Early consultation with the ESO before leasing the seabed can streamline grid connectivity timelines. A coordinated and systematic approach to grid development and offshore wind projects will expedite connectivity, enabling the Energy System Operator (ESO) to offer guidance on strategic seabed leasing following planned network design. This shift from reactive to planned grid deployment will, in turn, mitigate the risk of offshore wind assets becoming stranded.

Enhancing grid stability and implementing grid-forming solutions will reinforce the stability of floating offshore wind farms and provide the capability to emulate inertia within the energy system. Using grid-former converters will improve energy security and stability in wind farms by allowing them to shape the grid actively, serve as a foundational power resource, and swiftly restore stability following transient electrical events or outages. Integrating grid-forming controls ensures stability between floating offshore systems and the grid and contributes to an overall increase in energy security.

Integrating energy storage technologies, particularly hydrogen, through hybridisation offers a significant prospect for boosting revenues from developments and mitigating the variable generation profile of offshore wind power. Hydrogen storage introduces flexibility and potential inertia to the system, alleviating grid constraints and minimising the risk of turbine curtailment. Additionally, it offers generation capacity during periods of low wind resources. This promotes a competitive environment for floating offshore wind projects and contributes to decreased Levelized Cost of Energy (LCOE) and heightened returns for developers.

Colocation and spatial integration with other generation technologies, such as wave energy and floating solar, can reduce the intermittency of electricity output and enhance revenues from offshore wind projects. Substantial cost savings can be realised for both technologies through shared infrastructure, including sub-stations and cabling, and joint Operation and Maintenance (O&M) services. This synergy presents a distinctive opportunity for the commercialisation of floating solar and wave energy projects.

1. INTRODUCTION

Floating offshore wind is an essential technology that helps several countries meet their ambitious energy targets set worldwide. This is particularly relevant for nations like the UK and Germany, which have already established significant bottom-fixed capacity in shallow waters and aim to expand offshore wind energy production by using wind resources in deeper waters. Likewise, countries such as Italy and Greece, located in regions like the Mediterranean, where much of the offshore wind energy potential lies in deep waters, could benefit from adopting floating offshore wind technology. Figure 1 This highlights global ambitions for offshore wind, of which 69.7 GW of floating wind is planned for construction to start by 2040 and close globally.

Figure 1: Offshore wind global ambitions (Floating wind farms indicated with a blue icon) [6]

The United Kingdom has established a challenging goal of achieving 50 GW of offshore wind capacity by 2035, alongside full decarbonisation of its electricity sector by the same year, as it moves towards a low-carbon economy. Although most of the UK's offshore wind farms are based on bottom-fixed foundations limited to shallow waters, they face various technical, environmental, and public acceptance challenges. FOWTs present a promising solution to these limitations, with the potential to unlock deeper waters, benefit from more constant wind speeds, and mitigate the social impact of these installations.

In Italy, the National Integrated Climate and Energy Plan (2023) has set a target of 2.1 GW of installed wind capacity by 2030. The offshore wind energy potential is estimated at 16 and 20 GW. Due to the peculiarities of the Mediterranean Sea coasts and seabed, most of this capacity is expected to be realised with FOWTs. A total of 3.4 GW is planned for construction starting by 2040. [6].

However, deploying FOWTs presents significant technical challenges and barriers that must be overcome. This report provides an overview of the most relevant technological barriers affecting the development and deployment of and the status of technology development and research efforts. Several enablers that facilitate and/or accelerate the integration of FOWTs in the power systems have also been identified. This analysis results from a thorough literature survey considering the most relevant and up-to-date scientific production, industry reports, and interviews with relevant stakeholders and operators.

Floating offshore wind technology is relatively less mature than bottom offshore wind farms. More operational experience and historical data must be needed to assess performance, reliability, and long-term viability. The limited track record of floating wind farms can lead to higher costs, as developers and

investors may perceive higher risks. As a result, industrial actors still need to be convinced to develop components (e.g., the turbine) specifically designed for floating installation. This trend is already leading to technical issues and loss of performance. As the technology matures and more projects are deployed, learning curves will be achieved, and costs will decrease. As a result, there is a need for further research, development, and demonstration projects to prove the technology and build investor confidence.

There are only a few operational floating wind farms worldwide, most pilot or demonstration projects. With few projects to learn from, the industry needs help identifying best practices, optimising designs, and standardising components.

Various floating wind turbine platform designs, such as barge, spar buoy, semi-submersible, and tension leg platforms, are being tested and developed. As the industry continues experimenting with these designs, improvements will be made to enhance stability, reduce costs, and increase the efficiency of installation and operation.

Standardisation of components, such as floating platforms, mooring systems, and dynamic cables, is essential to reduce costs and streamline manufacturing processes. As the floating wind sector matures, industry players are expected to converge on standardised, more cost-effective, and widely available standardised components. Nevertheless, tailored designs suitable for the environmental conditions of different sea basins will be necessary.

As the industry gains experience deploying floating wind farms, installation and maintenance techniques will be improved. This includes optimising the methods for towing and anchoring floating platforms and developing more efficient monitoring and maintenance strategies that minimise downtime and operational costs. The widely developed expertise of the oil and gas industry is fundamental to reaching this target. Nevertheless, FOWTs show peculiarities (such as remote operation mode, control systems and dynamics, to provide a few examples) that devoted technical multidisciplinary approaches must tackle.

A mature industry typically has a well-established supply chain to support its technology's production, installation, and maintenance. The floating wind industry's supply chain is still developing, with opportunities for cost reductions and efficiency improvements as suppliers gain experience and expand their capabilities.

Technical maturity is often achieved through knowledge sharing and collaboration between industry stakeholders, including developers, manufacturers, regulators, and research institutions. As more floating wind projects are deployed, lessons learned can be shared to overcome challenges and improve the technology's performance and cost competitiveness.

Addressing these challenges is crucial for successfully developing and deploying floating wind farms. Key barriers identified in this report are:

1. **High costs:** Floating offshore wind technology is still in its early stages, and the costs associated with installation, operation, and maintenance are higher than traditional bottom-fixed offshore wind farms. As the technology matures and economies of scale are achieved, costs are expected to decrease.
2. **Grid connection and power transmission:** Connecting floating wind farms to the onshore grid can be complex, as they are typically located further from shore in deeper waters. Long-distance power transmission may require new undersea cable infrastructure and technologies, which can be costly and challenging to deploy.
3. **Installation and maintenance:** Installing, operating, and maintaining floating wind farms in remote and deepwater locations can be logistically challenging, requiring specialised vessels and equipment. Advances in installation techniques and maintenance strategies are necessary to overcome these challenges.
4. **Environmental impact:** Deploying floating wind farms may have environmental implications, such as impacts on marine life and ecosystems. Comprehensive environmental assessments are needed to understand and mitigate any potential negative effects.
5. **Regulatory and permitting challenges:** The UK regulatory framework for offshore wind energy projects may need to be adapted to accommodate floating wind farms. This may involve updating permitting processes, safety regulations, and environmental standards.
6. **Supply chain and manufacturing:** Developing a robust supply chain and manufacturing capabilities for floating wind turbine components is essential to support the industry's growth. This includes standardising designs, optimising manufacturing processes, and ensuring the availability of key components.
7. **Reliability and durability:** Floating wind turbines must be designed to withstand harsh ocean conditions, including strong winds, waves, and corrosive saltwater. Ensuring the long-term reliability and durability of these systems requires ongoing technological advancements.
8. **Public acceptance:** As with any new technology, public acceptance can be a barrier to deployment. Ensuring transparency in the planning process and engaging with stakeholders and local communities is essential for overcoming potential resistance to floating wind farm projects.

As the floating offshore wind industry matures, these aspects of technical maturity will improve, leading to reduced costs, increased efficiency, and greater commercial viability. Continuous investment in research, development, and demonstration projects is crucial to accelerating the industry's growth and helping it reach its full potential.

This document analyses the technological barriers and identifies enablers tailored to specific marine areas to facilitate the decarbonisation of the power system. It evaluates the challenges arising from the novel frontier of FOWTs, considering their correlation with regional geographical characteristics, impact on marine ecosystems, integration within the circular economy, and climate change. The report presents, in Chapter 2, the technological barriers and enablers, elaborating on key challenges to adoption.

2. TECHNOLOGICAL BARRIERS AND ENABLERS

This chapter provides a comprehensive overview of the current state and challenges facing the floating offshore wind sector. By merging detailed insights on the challenges and costs associated with FOWTs, the specific considerations of their offshore location, technological complexities, financial aspects, and a holistic understanding of the sector. This integrated approach highlights the inherent challenges and the potential pathways to make floating wind a more viable and competitive option in the renewable energy landscape, presenting a thorough examination of the floating offshore wind sector from multiple aspects impacting the energy system.

2.1. High Costs

Floating wind farms capitalise on stronger and more consistent wind resources that are available further offshore. This strategic advantage, however, comes with the significant challenge of transmitting power over longer distances, necessitating substantial investment in undersea cable infrastructure and advanced power transmission technologies. These requirements introduce additional complexity and cost to floating wind projects, affecting their financial viability and competitiveness.

Key factors to consider include:

- I. **Capital expenditures (CAPEX):** The specialised components required for FOWTs, including floating platforms, mooring systems, and dynamic power cables, are inherently more expensive than those used in traditional bottom-fixed installations. Moreover, the industry strategy is based on standard onshore or bottom-fixed machines for FOWT installations. Hence, the tailored design of wind turbines for floating applications is currently characterised by higher costs.

The construction and installation phases are not only technically challenging but also financially demanding, as evidenced by projects like Hywind [7]. The complexity of deploying these systems at scale further increases the CAPEX, making the initial investment significantly higher than that for conventional offshore wind farms.

- II. **Operational expenditures (OPEX):** Operating and maintaining floating wind farms can be more challenging due to their remote, deepwater locations. Specialised vessels and equipment may be needed to access and service these turbines, increasing operational costs. Furthermore, the harsh marine environment can increase wear and tear on turbine components, requiring more frequent maintenance and potentially higher replacement costs.
- III. **Financing:** The relative novelty of floating wind technology can make it more challenging to secure project financing, as there may be limited data available for investors to assess risk accurately. This can lead to higher financing costs or the need for more significant risk premiums, ultimately increasing the project's cost.

2.2. Grid connection and power transmission

Grid connection and power transmission are pivotal in offshore wind farms' development and operational efficiency, especially for FOWTs. These elements are instrumental in ensuring that the generated power

is efficiently transmitted to the grid, overcoming challenges related to distance, environmental conditions, and technical constraints. This section highlights key considerations, challenges, and advancements in grid connection and power transmission for FOWTs.

Key factors to consider include:

- I. **Distance from shore:** The cost of grid connection increases with the distance from the shore due to the need for longer undersea cables and more sophisticated technology to ensure minimal energy loss during transmission. For example, 1 km of pipeline in Italy costs around one million euros. Furthermore, rapid installation rates and the ambition to increase deployment targets add complexity to integrating offshore wind farms efficiently onto the onshore grid, posing spatial constraints. Innovative transmission technologies are currently facing these challenges. For instance, modular multilevel converters (MMCs) are widely used in flexible DC transmission due to their excellent control over power flow, low harmonic distortion, and high efficiency, even over long distances. Moreover, for connections exceeding 100 km, High Voltage Direct Current (HVDC) Systems are preferred due to their efficiency in long-distance transfers, despite the higher cost of converter stations [8].
- II. **Dynamic electrical infrastructure:** The cabling system of FOWTs endures harsh conditions and constant movement due to waves and currents throughout their lifespan. This situation not only calls for flexibility but also demands durability. Unlike static cables used in bottom-fixed developments, floating offshore wind requires dynamic, robust, and flexible cables to interconnect the turbines effectively. Critical components include dynamic cables, specialised connectors, protectors, and other ancillary equipment. Dynamic cables must be able to accommodate the extreme displacements that the floating offshore wind substation will encounter during a storm and have the fatigue stability to endure 20 years of service, whilst the choice of connector (wet-mate, dry-mate or break-away) connectors depends on the maintenance strategy. Breakaway designs are being developed to address the challenges of platform drift-off in floating offshore applications. These designs allow for decoupling at a specific load threshold, protecting the rest of the system from potential damage.
- III. **Subsea Cabling:** In large-scale commercial wind farms, energy generated by each turbine is collected and consolidated through an array of underwater cables leading to an offshore substation. These export cables, capable of spanning tens or hundreds of kilometres, are either buried beneath the seafloor, protected by armour, or routed using horizontal directional drilling when dealing with hard or rocky seabed or areas with steep bathymetry. The installation of subsea cables for floating wind farms can be challenging due to the need to account for variations in water depth, seabed conditions, and potential interference with marine life or existing infrastructure, such as shipping lanes or telecommunications cables. While in-water trenching technologies work well in soft sediments on the continental shelf, they may need to be more suitable for the harder seabed. Hazards associated with cables laid on the seafloor are identified through traditional geophysical data such as multibeam sonar and subbottom profilers. In regions where cables are trenched or exposed, uncertainties arise due to decreasing data resolution in

deeper waters, requiring additional technologies for hazard identification, avoidance, and mitigation in environmental assessments and engineering efforts.

Cable routing and installation require comprehensive seabed surveys, specialised equipment, and vessels, adding complexity and cost to the process. [9]. Additionally, the installation must consider potential impacts on marine ecosystems and adhere to environmental regulations and guidelines.

IV. **Inter-array Cabling:**

Inter-array cables connect the wind turbines within a wind farm. FOWTs have a dynamic section that adapts to the structure's movements, following a "lazy wave" configuration to manage both the horizontal movement of the turbines and the loads from the entire water column and seabed abrasion. These cables can be buried or anchored with rocks or protective matting at the seabed. There are three main methods for incorporating the dynamic section of the cable: a single dynamic cable between turbines, dynamic cables at each turbine connected by static lengths through joints or connectors, or a single assembly combining both types. The choice among these options depends on cost comparisons and evaluating potential failure points. In deep waters, cables can be suspended along their entire length, which could be advantageous for cable loading and reducing the required length, especially at depths around 500 meters. Currently, cables are rated at 66 kV. Still, an increase to 132 kV is anticipated to accommodate turbines rated at and above 16 MW more efficiently and to reduce the number of cable strings needed.

- V. **Platform designs:** Various floating platform designs, such as spar buoy, semi-submersible, and tension leg platforms, are being explored and tested. R&D efforts in this area focus on optimising these designs for stability, efficiency, and cost-effectiveness while considering specific site conditions, water depths, and environmental factors.

Mooring and anchoring systems: Developing robust and cost-effective mooring systems is essential for the long-term stability and reliability of floating wind turbines. R&D efforts aim to improve mooring systems' design, materials, and installation techniques to reduce costs, minimise environmental impacts, and increase durability.

Dynamic cables and connectors: Developing advanced dynamic cables and connectors is crucial for reliable power transmission from floating wind turbines to the onshore grid. R&D in this area focuses on materials, designs, and protection measures that can withstand continuous motion and harsh marine conditions while maintaining optimal performance and longevity.

- VI. **Offshore Substations** play a critical role in transmitting the electricity generated by offshore wind turbines to the onshore grid. The floating offshore wind farms require specialised offshore substations that can withstand harsh marine environments and accommodate the unique challenges of floating turbine platforms. Designing efficient, cost-effective substation solutions is crucial to enable the rapid scale-up of floating wind projects. Standardisation and modularisation [10] [11]. Key R&D efforts are needed in:

- a. Developing innovative floating substation designs that can be efficiently integrated with floating wind turbine platforms, including optimising the substation's size, weight, and stability to work seamlessly with the floating wind structures.
- b. Grid interconnection and transmission Research to address the technical challenges of transmitting power from offshore floating wind farms to the onshore grid, including dynamic cable design, offshore-to-onshore transmission, and grid integration.
- c. Improving the reliability and maintainability of offshore substations, as access and servicing can be more challenging for floating structures than fixed-bottom offshore wind.

Innovations in remote monitoring, predictive maintenance, and modular designs can enhance substation uptime.

- d. Developing standardised, mass-producible floating substation designs and manufacturing processes can help reduce costs and enable the rapid deployment of floating offshore wind projects.

VII. **Grid integration** is critical to support the acceleration of floating offshore wind deployment. Proactive grid integration planning, innovative grid management solutions, and efficient permitting and interconnection processes are critical to enable the rapid deployment of floating offshore wind and unlock its full potential. Key aspects to consider:

- a. **Proactive Grid Planning:** Coordinated grid infrastructure planning between offshore wind developers, transmission system operators, and regulators is essential to ensure timely and efficient grid integration of floating offshore wind farms. Proactive planning is critical to support the rapid deployment of floating offshore wind and unlock its full potential.
- b. **Grid Reliability and Flexibility:** Integrating large amounts of variable, inverter-based offshore wind generation poses grid reliability and stability challenges. Innovative solutions, such as energy storage, flexible generation, and advanced grid control technologies, are needed to maintain grid reliability and flexibility.
- c. **Streamlined Permitting and Interconnection:** Streamlined, well-defined, and transparent permitting and interconnection processes are required to accelerate the development of necessary grid infrastructure to support offshore wind deployment. Coordination between different regulatory bodies is crucial.
- d. **Floating-Specific Considerations:** Floating offshore wind farms may be located further from shore, requiring longer submarine cables and additional offshore substations. This adds complexity and costs to the grid integration process, which needs to be addressed.
- e. **Complexity in Integration:** Integrating a high share of renewable energy, such as floating offshore wind, requires long-duration flexibility to manage the variability of these resources and maintain grid stability.
- f. **Environmental Impacts and Energy Security:** An integrated offshore grid that serves both as a connection for wind farms and as an interconnector offers advantages such as economies of scale, reduced environmental impacts, and enhanced energy security compared to separate radial connections.

2.3. Design, Operations, Maintenance, and Decommissioning

Installation and maintenance of floating offshore wind turbines present unique challenges compared to bottom-fixed configurations. As floating wind technology is less mature, addressing these challenges is crucial to ensure efficient deployment and long-term operation of floating wind farms [12]. R&D efforts aim to develop innovative methods and tools to streamline these processes, reduce downtime, and lower costs. This includes advancements in remote monitoring, predictive maintenance, robotics, and automation to minimise human intervention and improve overall operational efficiency. Key challenges include:

I. Design:

The design of floating wind turbines and wind farms is complex and multidisciplinary, requiring expertise in structural engineering, naval architecture, offshore engineering, and renewable energy systems. Thus, the challenge for cost reduction and Operation & Maintenance optimisation must be tackled in a multidisciplinary context involving the interaction among rotary-wing aerodynamics, tower/blades structural dynamics, floater-waves interaction phenomena, cable and mooring dynamics, control strategies and grid connection optimisation. A consistent prediction of wind farm performance is the result of a comprehensive analysis. For these reasons and given the costs and complexity of devoted experimental tests, reliable and accurate numerical tools are complementary to address floating offshore wind turbine design. Advanced simulation models are available and continuously improved, but the occurrence of accidents pushes technology developers to deploy full-scale prototypes before commercial wind farms [13]. The main technological barriers related to FOWT components design are discussed below:

a. Wind turbine

Designing wind turbines tailored for installation on floating platforms presents several specific challenges compared to traditional bottom-fixed machines. These challenges arise from the dynamic nature of the marine environment. Indeed, the operating conditions of floating offshore wind turbines are more severe than on land. The reasons are twofold: i) the highly unsteady aero loads induced by wind strength, arising and falling sporadically; ii) the sea motion, continuously modifying the placement of the rotor disk to the wind direction. It is proven that the presence of wind shear, turbulence, yaw misalignment, tower shadow and platform translational/rotational motion give rise to strong, unsteady aerodynamic phenomena such as skewed wake flow, dynamic stall and rotor-wake interaction [14].

The feasibility of different technology approaches must be assessed by multi-fidelity tools and design methods that can accurately represent FOWTs in an integrated fashion. Many of these tools already exist, but improvements are needed to address the complex challenges posed by the sea environment [15].

The lower maturity of FOWT for the bottom-fixed and onshore technologies represents a significant economic risk factor for turbine systems developers and manufacturers. Within an unhealthy cycle, this aspect holds back the development and design of wind turbines tailored for floating platform installation. State-of-the-art machines deployed in floating wind farms are designed for onshore or bottom-fixed conditions. A floating machine structure must be robust enough to withstand the dynamic loads imposed by wind, waves, and currents while also being lightweight to minimise costs. Hence, structural integrity and fatigue life become critical considerations and understanding the dynamic response of the turbine to various environmental conditions is vital for optimising its performance and ensuring its structural integrity over its operational lifetime [16] [17].

b. Platform design types

Several different platform design types are currently being investigated and prototyped. Designs are focused on maximising platform stability and reducing motion, which is crucial for the efficient operation of wind turbines. Furthermore, many platforms aim to reduce costs through innovative design features, such as reducing material weight, increasing the power-to-weight ratio, and adopting modular designs for easier serial production. Some platforms are designed with local conditions in mind, using locally sourced materials like concrete instead of steel to lower costs and meet local supply chain capabilities.

On the other hand, technological challenges related to platform design and manufacturing still exist. Despite the potential for cost reduction, the initial Levelised Cost of Energy for floating offshore wind remains high due to design and fabrication complexity, increased mass, and additional maintenance requirements. The innovative designs aimed at stability, motion reduction, and cost savings add complexity to the engineering, manufacturing, and installation processes, potentially leading to higher upfront costs and logistical challenges. Besides, the need for an industrial standardisation of platform designs for specific metocean conditions contributes to the high manufacturing costs. Finally, floating platforms require more maintenance and operational oversight due to their exposure to marine conditions and the motion of the sea, which can lead to higher long-term costs compared to fixed platforms.

However, projections suggest a significant decrease in LCOE over time as the technology matures and operational efficiencies improve. Technological features and challenges related to the current platform design concepts are listed in the following:

Spar Platforms: These platforms use gravity stabilisation. They are characterised by a single vertical cylinder with ballast at the bottom, connecting directly to the wind turbine tower. This design offers excellent stability in deep water but has high construction and installation costs due to its size and the need for specialised vessels for towing and installation.

Semi-submersible: These platforms are designed to achieve stability through buoyancy and weight distribution across a broader area. Semi-subs are versatile for various water depths and conditions, balancing stability and cost. However, their complex design can increase manufacturing and maintenance expenses.

Tension Leg Platforms (TLPs): These platforms use mooring stabilisation with taut moorings connected to a submerged body. TLPs are highly stable and can significantly reduce motion, making them ideal for supporting wind turbines. The downside is the complexity and cost of their mooring systems, especially in very deep waters.

Barge Platforms: These platforms rely on waterplane stabilisation. They have a shallow draft, making them suitable for various water depths. Barges are cost-effective for manufacturing and installation but may require more active motion-dampening systems to ensure stability, increasing operational costs.

Figure 2: Platform design types for floating offshore wind [14]

The strengths and weaknesses of these types of platforms are summarised in Table 1, overleaf.

Table 1: Pros and Cons of Floating offshore wind platform design types

Platform type	Pros	Cons
Spar	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – inherent stability – suitable for even higher sea states – soil condition insensitivity – cheap & simple mooring & anchoring system – low operational risk 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – large motions – unsuitable for shallow water – large seabed footprint – long mooring lines (costs) – assembly in sheltered deep water.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - little susceptible to corrosion - simple structure, easy manufacturing & maintenance 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - challenging, time-consuming & costly float-out & installation - long & heavy structure (costs) - high fatigue loads in the tower base
Semi-sub	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - heave plates for reducing heave response - broad weather window for float-out & installation - depth independence - soil condition insensitivity - cheap & simple mooring & anchoring system - low overall risk - onshore or dry dock assembly - simple installation & decommissioning 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - lower stability, higher motions - wave sensitivity - large seabed footprint - long mooring lines (costs) - subject to corrosion & ice-loads - large & complex structure, more challenging manufacturing & maintenance - large & heavy structure (costs) - larger impact on the turbine due to motions
TLP	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - high stability, low motions - little wave sensitivity (in case of submerged platform) - suitable for even high sea states (in case of submerged platform) - suitable for intermediate depths - small seabed footprint - short mooring lines - little susceptible to corrosion (in case of submerged platform) - simple, small & light structure, easy maintenance - onshore or dry dock assembly 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - unsuitable for strong tidal currents or storm surges - unsuitable for shallow water - unsuitable for challenging soil conditions - complex & costly mooring & anchoring system - There is a high risk if the tendon or anchor fails - complex & risky installation & disconnection for onshore maintenance - large stresses in structure
Barge	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Low-cost production - Easy geometries - Depth independence - Simple mooring system - Motion Reduction - Flat without interspaces - Full system easy transportation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Launching technique - No global market position. - Large dimensions for future 15 MW+ turbines - Heavy structure

c. Moorings and anchoring systems

Mooring and anchoring systems are critical for the operation of floating platforms. They secure them in place and allow for the necessary movement and flexibility. These systems are designed to withstand environmental loads from waves, currents, and wind.

The mooring system fixes and flexibly connects the floating platform to the anchoring point on the seabed. These components are generally made of chains, fibre ropes, wire ropes, or synthetic cables. The choice between the different types of mooring depends on factors such as the depth of the water, the type of floating platform, and the weather conditions (waves, currents, winds). Below are the mooring types currently used:

- **Catenary:** This anchor or cable takes on a specific shape when not under tension, influenced primarily by its weight. This is the most common type, where the moorings are not tensioned beyond their weight load. Depending on water depth, platform movement restrictions, and materials used, floats and weights can be added to change the shape of the catenary into "S" or similar (lazy wave) configurations. Typically, the length of the catenary is three times the depth of the water at the installation point.
- **Tensioned mooring:** in this case, a mooring catenary is mechanically tensioned to reduce the mooring footprint (area of seabed affected), the length of cable or chain used, and to increase restrictions on the movement of the floating platform.
- **TLP (Tensioned Leg Platform):** TLP anchors work differently than tensioned catenaries. They involve cables and are suitable for great depths due to the associated material savings.

The anchors act as components that connect the moorings to the seabed, a crucial aspect of floating offshore wind turbines. Their choice depends on the characteristics and loads of the seabed. Accurate geotechnical and geological assessments are fundamental and decisive in defining the type most suitable for the chosen installation site. Going into more detail, the main anchoring types are listed below:

Drag anchors: Like those used by ships, this system supports tension in one direction within a certain angle of tolerance. Its positive aspects are that it resists horizontal loads and is easy to install and uninstall.

Suction buckets: These are steel structures, often cylindrical and open at the bottom end, which rely on suction to create a pressure difference (vacuum) for anchoring. They work effectively on bottoms with a balanced texture (sandy or sandy-loamy) but are unsuitable for rocky or coarse-grained bottoms. Those predominantly vertical are called suction piles, while those with a square geometry are called suction caissons.

Driven or drilled piles: Identical to the structures used in fixed foundations, these are large hollow metal cylinders driven into the seabed. Installation may require drilling into rocky or hard ground, which involves noise and the production of suspended sediment. In floating wind projects, their use is limited to locations where other alternatives could be more practical.

Fixed or gravity anchors are imposing concrete structures placed on the seabed. Given their large footprint on the seabed, they are considerable in size. Given their use, they are limited to specific situations to minimise impact.

Cables and substation: There are several considerations in the design aspects of cables and large-scale commercial wind farms: the energy generated by individual turbines is collected and consolidated through a series of underwater export cables leading to an offshore substation. These export cables can cover tens or hundreds of kilometres and are typically buried beneath the seabed for protection. The cables may be routed using horizontal directional drilling instead of in-water excavation in the hard or rocky seabed or steep bathymetry areas. Geophysical data such as multibeam sonar and subbottom profilers are used to identify hazards associated with seafloor cables. In deeper waters, decreasing data resolution can lead to uncertainties, requiring additional technologies for hazard identification, avoidance, and mitigation.

- **Inter-array cables** in floating offshore wind farms have a dynamic section that adapts to the movements of the floating structure. These cables follow a "lazy wave" configuration to manage both the horizontal movement of the turbines and the loads arising from the entire water column and seabed abrasion. The cables can be buried or anchored at the seabed with rocks or protective mats. There are three main methods for incorporating the dynamic cable section: a single dynamic cable between turbines, dynamic cables on each turbine connected by static lengths via joints or connectors, or a single assembly combining both types. The choice between these options depends on cost comparison and evaluating potential failure points. In deep water, the cables can be suspended along their entire length, which could be advantageous regarding cable load and reduction of the required length, especially at depths around 500 metres.
- **Voltage Rating:** The cables are currently rated at 66 kV. However, an increase to 132 kV is expected to accommodate turbines of 16 MW or more efficiently and reduce the required cable strings.
- **Offshore substation** acts as a central hub, receiving the power from the inter-array cables and transmitting it through the export cables to the onshore substation. These substations typically include transformers to increase the voltage from the medium-voltage inter-array cables to the high-voltage export cables, switchgear, control systems, and other electrical equipment. Offshore substations are critical components as they enable efficient power transmission from the wind farm to the onshore grid.

II. Installation

The installation of floating platforms is complex and requires careful logistics consideration. Moreover, specialised vessels, equipment, and expertise to handle the floating platforms, mooring/anchoring systems, and dynamic cables are required in this process. The advantages of floating platforms being assembled onshore or in sheltered waters, which can significantly reduce the cost and complexity of installation, are summarised in Table 2. This approach allows for the integration of wind turbines onto floating structures in a controlled environment, enhancing safety and efficiency before towing the assembled units to their final location [7] [16] [18] [19] [20] [21] [22].

Table 2: Installation considerations for different floating design types

Spar type:	Semi-submersible type:	Tension Leg Platforms:
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – High draught makes towing difficult. – Requires heavy lift vessels – Unstable motion of floater during mating – High installation cost – Tighter weather constraints – Requires deep water ports and sheltered areas. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Easy installation – Fully assembled at quayside – Cheaper mooring and anchoring system – Short installation time – Low installation cost – More sensitive to wave height limits during towing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Can be completely constructed onshore. – Complex mooring and anchoring system – Slow and lengthy installation process – High installation cost – Bespoke barge required. – High environmental impact

- a. **Platform stability during installation:** Platform stability during installation is paramount for the operation's safety and the structure's integrity. Floating platforms must be designed to maintain stability under various conditions, including transit to the site and the installation process. The stability of these platforms is ensured through advanced design and engineering practices, considering factors such as buoyancy, weight distribution, and the effects of wind and waves.

- b. **Mooring and anchoring systems:** Installing this sub-system for floating wind turbines can be challenging due to the need to ensure proper tensioning, alignment, and connection to the floating platforms. This may involve remotely operated vehicles (ROVs) or divers to assist in the installation process and verify the correct positioning and secure attachment of mooring lines and anchors. Several types of mooring systems have been proposed for FOWTs, including single-point, multi-point, and hybrid mooring systems. Each system has its advantages and disadvantages in terms of stability, flexibility, and cost. For example, single point mooring systems can offer greater flexibility in terms of platform response but may require more complex control systems and pose challenges for installation and maintenance. Multi-point mooring systems can offer greater stability and redundancy but may require more space and materials and pose challenges for system integration and optimisation [23].

- c. **Dynamic cable installation:** The dynamic cable installation is essential for connecting the floating platforms to the seabed, the electrical grid onshore and the (floating) substation. These cables must be highly flexible and durable to accommodate the movement of the platforms and the harsh marine environment. More specifically, installing these cables can be challenging due to their constant motion and the need to ensure adequate slack and bend radius to prevent excessive stress and fatigue. Specialised cable handling equipment and techniques may be required to ensure dynamic cables' successful installation and long-term performance.

III. Operation & Maintenance

- a. **Wind farm operation and control:** Designing control systems for floating offshore wind farms presents several technological challenges due to the complex and dynamic nature of the marine environment. In detail, control systems must continuously adjust the turbine's orientation and the platform's position to minimise motion and maintain stability. Furthermore, platform motion can significantly affect turbine performance and structural integrity. Thus, control systems must be designed to mitigate these effects by adjusting the turbine's rotor speed, blade pitch, and yaw

angle to minimise loads on the structure and optimise power production. Advanced control algorithms, such as model predictive control (MPC) or adaptive control, may be required to handle floating turbines' nonlinear and time-varying behaviour.

On the floater side of the system, controls must actively manage the tension and alignment of mooring lines to maintain platform position and stability. Dynamic positioning systems (DPS) may be employed to control the platform's position relative to the desired location.

Finally, farm-level control systems are even more important than bottom-fixed applications to maximise power production by minimising wake/turbine detrimental interactions within the farm due to the inherent unsteady behaviour of floating turbines' wakes.

- b. **Maintenance access:** Maintenance access is a crucial aspect of floating offshore wind farms, ensuring that personnel can safely and efficiently reach the platforms for routine inspections, repairs, and component replacements. Access to the platforms for maintenance can be more challenging than bottom-fixed turbines, particularly in rough sea conditions [19] [21] [22]. This may require specialised vessels, such as crew transfer vessels or service operation vessels, or alternative access methods, such as helicopters or remotely operated maintenance systems, to ensure safe and efficient access to the turbines [24]. Specific maintenance access issues related to different platform types are listed in Table 3.

Table 3: Specific access issues by floating design types

Spar Type	Semi-submersible Type	Tension Leg Platforms
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Similar to bottom-fixed wind turbines – Heavy-lift vessels might be required for major repairs. – Needs deep water ports and sheltered areas for repairs. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Simple unhook from the mooring system. – Can be towed back to the quayside for major repairs. – No heavy-lift vessels required. – Helicopter access possible 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Difficult to unhook, more onsite repairs. – Mooring system highly susceptible to failure

- c. **Maintenance of mooring and anchoring systems:** Regular inspection and maintenance are crucial to ensure long-term performance and prevent failures. This may involve using underwater inspection techniques, such as ROVs, divers, or autonomous underwater vehicles (AUVs), to assess the condition of mooring lines, anchors, and other subsea components.
- d. **Condition monitoring and predictive maintenance:** The adoption of condition monitoring and predictive maintenance strategies is highlighted as an effective means to enhance the reliability and performance of floating offshore wind farms. By continuously monitoring the condition of key components, including the mooring and anchoring systems, operators can predict potential failures and perform targeted maintenance, thereby reducing the risk of unexpected downtime, improving overall efficiency, and reducing maintenance costs. This can involve using sensors, data analytics, and machine learning algorithms to monitor the health of critical components and predict their remaining useful life. To this aim, digital twins for the single machine or the full farm

synthesised using operational data and/or numerical models are fundamental to achieve predictive maintenance for the system and prevent major failures and downtime.

IV. **Decommissioning:**

Decommissioning is a crucial phase in the lifecycle of any offshore wind farm, including floating wind farms. It involves safely and efficiently removing all infrastructure, equipment, and structures from the site once the wind farm's operational lifespan ends.

Decommissioning begins with removing all wind turbines, substructures, mooring systems, and associated infrastructure. Specialised vessels with heavy lifting equipment dismantle and lift components from the seabed. Turbines are typically disassembled into manageable sections for transportation to shore for recycling or disposal.

The decommissioning process of the floaters depends on their specific design. In detail, spar-type platforms are partially decommissioned in deep water, requiring heavy-lift vessels. Differently, semi-submersible and barge types, using easily recoverable drag-embedded anchors, can be completely towed back to shore for dismantling without needing heavy-lift vessels. Finally, the dismantling of Tension Leg Platforms is more cumbersome due to their complex mooring system and their non-recoverable pile-driven anchors [19] [21].

Concerning submarine power cables decommissioning and removal, burial depths are often specified to minimise the risk of exposure or damage during the operational phase, making cable retrieval a specialised task requiring careful planning and execution. Specialised vessels equipped with cable laying and cutting tools are required. Precision cutting techniques are employed to sever the cables at designated points, eventually involving remotely operated vehicles (ROVs) to ensure accuracy and minimise the risk of damaging surrounding infrastructures. Cables must then be lifted from the seabed using lifting equipment attached to the vessels to prevent entanglement with marine life or damage to the seabed during the process. Finally, removed cables are transported to designated facilities for recycling or disposal according to environmental regulations. Recycling efforts aim to recover valuable materials such as copper or aluminium, reducing the environmental footprint of the decommissioning process [22] [24].

In general, waste generated during decommissioning, including metal components, cables, and other materials, must be managed per environmental regulations. Recycling and disposal options are evaluated to minimise the environmental impact of waste disposal.

Once all infrastructure has been removed, site remediation activities may be necessary to restore the seabed to its pre-development condition. This may involve seabed levelling, sediment stabilisation, and habitat restoration measures to promote the recovery of marine ecosystems.

2.4. Supply chain and manufacturing

Developing a robust and efficient supply chain is essential for the growth of the floating offshore wind industry. Some of the most relevant technological barriers are actual manufacturing costs and suitable

areas for component assembly. R&D in this area focuses on standardising components, streamlining manufacturing processes, and exploring new materials to reduce costs and increase the availability of key components. The following key challenges are envisaged:

- I. **Standardisation of components:** The floating wind industry currently features various platform designs, such as spar buoy, semi-submersible, and tension leg platforms. Furthermore, turbines specifically tailored for floating wind applications are not being designed yet. This is, to some extent, related to the actual market risk of FOWT installations. The lack of standardised components and designs can lead to inefficiencies in manufacturing processes, increased costs, and a limited supplier base. Developing standardised components and designs can help streamline manufacturing processes, reduce costs, and facilitate the large-scale deployment of floating wind farms.
- II. **Specialised components:** Floating wind farms require unique components, such as floating platforms, mooring and anchoring systems, and dynamic cables, which may not be readily available in the existing supply chain. Developing manufacturing capabilities and expertise for these specialised components is crucial to meeting the growing demand and ensuring the industry's long-term success.
- III. **Port infrastructure:** Adequate port facilities are essential for efficiently installing floating offshore wind turbines. Ports must have suitable quaysides, storage areas, and load-out capabilities to accommodate the large components and equipment. The availability of suitable port infrastructure in the UK and in MARINEWIND partner countries may be limited, posing a challenge for installing floating wind farms [25].

The UK has been investing significantly in port infrastructure to support the growth of the offshore wind industry. Several ports have been upgraded or are being upgraded to meet the requirements of offshore wind projects, including floating offshore wind farms.

Key ports that play a crucial role in the UK's offshore wind sector, for instance, include:

- Port of Hull: This port has been developed into a centre for offshore wind manufacturing, assembly, and logistics. The Siemens Gamesa factory in Hull manufactures wind turbine blades, and the port provides ample space for the assembly and storage of components.
- Port of Grimsby: Grimsby serves as an operations and maintenance hub for several offshore wind farms. The port has invested in facilities to support the servicing and maintenance of offshore wind turbines.
- Port of Lowestoft: Lowestoft is another operations and maintenance hub for offshore wind farms in the southern North Sea. The port has facilities to support wind farm installation vessels and maintenance crews.
- Port of Great Yarmouth: This port has been developed to support the construction and installation of offshore wind farms. It offers facilities for the storage, assembly, and loading of wind turbine components and has the capacity to accommodate large installation vessels.

- Port of Blyth: Blyth is home to the Offshore Renewable Energy (ORE) Catapult's National Renewable Energy Centre, which focuses on offshore wind research, innovation, and testing. The port also provides facilities for the manufacturing and assembly of wind turbines and subsea structures.

Similarly, in Italy, the public competent bodies have identified two ports that will serve as hubs for deploying floating offshore wind farms. The measures to tailor these ports to the actual needs of FOWT are planned for the near future. In detail, within the Article 8 (Misure per lo sviluppo della filiera relativa agli impianti eolici galleggianti in mare) of DECRETO-LEGGE 9 dicembre 2023, n. 181 (LEGGE 2 febbraio 2024, n. 11) the financial support for the development of two ports in central and southern Italy for the supply chain of FOWT. At the moment, the location of these ports has not been disclosed.

- IV. **Manufacturing processes:** Optimising manufacturing processes for floating wind turbine components can help improve efficiency, reduce waste, and lower production costs. However, the industry's relatively nascent stage may limit the adoption of advanced manufacturing techniques, such as automation, additive manufacturing, and modular construction, which can result in reduced lead times and increased production capacity [26].
- Lightweight and Cost-Effective Design:** The continuous market push for lower levelised energy cost requires all wind turbine system components to be as light and cost-effective as possible while maintaining safety, performance, and reliability requirements. The current technological trend is towards larger and larger machines, with blades and towers increasing in structural capacity through material and design advances. This has resulted in lighter and dynamically softer components, which may get closer to aeroelastic coupling interactions and instability boundaries. Similarly, drivetrain technologies have become more torque-dense and reliable even as their size increases.
 - Addressing Design and Manufacturing Challenges:** Many design and manufacturing challenges remain. The tools and underlying design assumptions used to manufacture the successful but costly, stiff, and bulky systems of the past need to be validated for new design strategies and limits related to floating wind installations. Improved materials and manufacturing methods offer options that need to be proven at scale to get to market. New modelling and analysis approaches are needed to bring higher-fidelity capabilities incorporating more physics, capturing coupled integrated systems, and supporting both deterministic and probabilistic optimisation aspects into the design process.
 - Experimental Validation and Design Process Updates: Bespoke** experimental campaigns are required to validate simulation capabilities for design purposes. The design process needs to be updated to leverage best the improved understanding of the physical phenomena affecting floating offshore wind turbine (FOWT) behaviour.
 - Holistic Optimisation Considerations:** FOWT economic optimisation must consider the wind turbines and wind farm's overall life cycle. Optimised machines can be designed that include many other considerations beyond the levelized cost of energy, such as the controllability of the wind power plant, the carbon-dioxide emissions generated during production, installation, and decommissioning, the recyclability of the wind turbine at the end of life; the reuse or repurposing of components; and the impact on the environment and the economy.
 - Simulation-Driven Design and Manufacturing:** In terms of optimising the manufacturing process, simulation technology through numerical prototyping is the key enabler for

shorter times to market. With general, comprehensive, robust, and reliable validated simulation tools, a closer match between design predictions and actual field behaviour can be achieved, leading to fewer physical prototypes. The simulation also enables customisation to site-specific conditions and the evaluation of design innovations that cannot be tested on physical prototypes until they are known to have a high probability of success.

- f.* **Improved Design and Manufacturing processes** can reduce the need to rely on safety factors and achieve minimal failures, higher safety, and increased availability. With obvious positive economic implications, this can activate a healthy cycle that lowers financing and insurance costs and reduces liability.
- V. **Local content and regional supply chains:** Developing regional supply chains and leveraging local manufacturing capabilities can significantly benefit the offshore wind industry. This approach can help create local jobs and stimulate economic growth while reducing transportation costs and environmental impacts associated with the long-distance shipping of components. Additionally, the specific design and materials used for component construction, such as concrete or steel, can be optimised to improve local manufacturability. However, establishing a robust local supply chain may be challenging, particularly in regions with limited infrastructure or lacking offshore wind manufacturing expertise. Building these regional capabilities can be difficult in areas without a strong industrial base or experience in the offshore wind sector. Overcoming these hurdles will be crucial for realising the full advantages of local content and regional supply chains [27].
- VI. **Critical raw materials:** The scarcity of certain critical raw materials is critical for constructing floating offshore wind farms. These rare earth elements and high-performance steel materials are essential for turbine manufacturing and support structures. These materials' limited availability and uneven global distribution create supply chain vulnerabilities and geopolitical risks, as many are concentrated in a few countries. Additionally, the extraction and processing of these critical raw materials often involve environmentally damaging practices that can harm local ecosystems and communities [28].

To address these challenges, exploring new materials and low-carbon material combinations for floating wind turbine components could improve performance, durability, and cost-effectiveness. However, the current state of material research and development and concerns about their long-term reliability in the harsh marine environment may limit the adoption of innovative materials. Continued investment in material R&D is necessary to overcome these limitations and ensure the viability of new materials for floating offshore wind applications [29].

Addressing the critical raw materials issue and fostering material innovation will be crucial for the floating offshore wind industry to develop more sustainable and cost-effective solutions for the construction and operation of these wind farms. The industry can enhance floating offshore wind projects' resilience and environmental performance by diversifying the supply of critical materials and advancing material technologies.
- VII. **Quality assurance and certification:** Ensuring the quality and reliability of floating wind turbine components is essential for successfully deploying and operating floating wind farms. However, the lack of established standards and certification processes specific to floating wind technology may pose challenges in demonstrating compliance with industry requirements and building confidence in the technology [30].

VIII. **Collaboration and partnerships:** Fostering collaboration between component manufacturers, wind farm developers, research institutions, and government agencies can help share knowledge, resources, and expertise, accelerating the development and deployment of floating wind technology. However, establishing effective partnerships and collaborations can be challenging, particularly in a competitive market environment and in the absence of supportive policy frameworks.

2.5. Reliability and durability

Reliability and durability are critical factors for successfully deploying and operating floating offshore wind farms. As floating wind technology is less mature than bottom-fixed offshore wind, addressing concerns related to the reliability and durability of the components and systems is essential to build confidence in the technology, ensure long-term performance, and reduce operational risks. Reliability and durability are critical factors for successfully deploying and operating floating offshore wind farms. As floating wind technology is less mature than bottom-fixed offshore wind, addressing concerns related to the reliability and durability of the components and systems is essential to building confidence in the technology, ensuring long-term performance, and reducing operational risks [31].

Durability in FOWTs is influenced by the materials used in their construction and the environmental conditions they endure. Innovations in material science, such as exploring alternative materials like carbon fibre composites for substructures, offer pathways to increase structural stiffness, longevity, and durability at sea. The durability of FOWTs is also critically dependent on their design to withstand the fatigue load environment, including turbine top motion and control loading to minimise energy production curtailment.

The main challenges to reliability and durability in floating offshore wind farms include:

- **Environmental Stressors:** FOWTs face significant challenges from their operating environment, including high wind speeds, waves, and marine growth, which can lead to accelerated wear and tear.
- **Maintenance and Access:** The remote nature of offshore installations complicates routine maintenance and emergency repairs, impacting the turbines' reliability and durability.
- **System Complexity:** The complexity of FOWTs, including their mooring systems, electrical systems, and dynamic positioning, adds layers of potential failure points that require sophisticated management strategies to ensure reliability and durability.

The main strategies for enhancing reliability and durability in floating offshore wind farms include:

- **Advanced Monitoring and Predictive Maintenance:** Employing advanced sensor technologies and predictive analytics can significantly improve the early detection of potential failures, enhancing reliability and durability.
- **Innovative Design and Material Use:** Integrating innovative design approaches that consider FOWTs' unique operational challenges and using durable materials can enhance their resilience against environmental stressors.

- **Operational Optimisation:** Strategies that optimise the operation of FOWTs, including adjusting to weather conditions and minimising wear and tear through intelligent control systems, are crucial for improving reliability and durability.
- **Testing and Certification:** Rigorous testing and certification of floating wind turbine components and systems can help ensure their reliability and durability under various operating conditions. This includes laboratory testing, numerical simulations, and full-scale prototype testing to validate performance, identify potential issues, and demonstrate compliance with industry standards and regulations. By addressing these key factors and implementing these strategies, the reliability and durability of floating offshore wind farms can be significantly enhanced, leading to improved long-term performance and reduced operational risks.

The key reliability and durability considerations for FOWT sub-systems are:

- **Wind turbine:** Reliability analysis of turbine components is well-established for onshore and bottom-fixed applications, but limited data exists for FOWTs due to their recent deployment. Components like generators and mechanical brakes are more prone to weather-related damage in the marine environment. The presence of saltwater is expected to increase corrosion and failure rates, requiring further development to mitigate these issues.
- **Floating platform:** The reliability and durability of floating platforms are crucial, as they must withstand harsh marine environments, including high winds, waves, and currents. Different floating platform designs like spar buoys, semi-submersibles, and tension leg platforms have unique strengths and challenges. For instance, the Spar-type platform (now the most mature technology) faces small heave motion but higher pitch and roll amplitudes than other designs. Differently, the Tension Leg Platform, Semi-submersible, and Barge types face small roll and pitch motion, leading to more stable operating conditions [32]. In addition, TLP manufacturing uses lighter materials for other types of solutions. This yields lower load levels on the turbine mechanical sub-systems (rotor, gearbox), thus enhancing reliability and durability. On the other hand, catastrophic failure risk is envisaged for the TLP if one mooring line fails, whilst large fatigue loads on the bottom are expected for the Spar type. Finally, larger heave motion, which could affect stability in certain conditions, is ascribable to the Semi-sub/Barge platforms. Optimising these designs for specific site conditions can help improve their long-term performance and durability.
- **Mooring and anchoring systems:** Floating wind turbines rely on mooring and anchoring systems to maintain their position and stability. Ensuring the reliability and durability of these systems is vital to prevent failures that could damage the turbine, platform, or subsea infrastructure. This includes selecting appropriate materials, designing for redundancy, and conducting regular inspections and maintenance.
- **Dynamic cables:** Floating wind turbines require dynamic cables to transmit electricity from the turbines to the seabed, which are subjected to constant motion due to the movement of the floating platform. Designing and manufacturing durable, fatigue-resistant dynamic cables is crucial to ensure reliable power transmission and reduce the risk of cable failures, which can be costly to repair.

- **Corrosion protection:** Floating wind turbine components, particularly those in contact with seawater, are susceptible to corrosion, which can compromise their structural integrity and lead to premature failure. Implementing effective corrosion protection measures, such as protective coatings and cathodic protection, and selecting corrosion-resistant materials can help improve these components' durability and long-term performance [33].

2.6. Ongoing Research and Development

Ongoing research and development are essential for advancing floating wind technology and overcoming associated challenges, which can be costly. Public and private sector investments in research, pilot projects, and technology demonstrations are crucial for reducing costs over time.

Key areas of focus for R&D in offshore floating wind technology primarily include wind turbine and wind farm designs and floating platform designs, including the study and analysis of mooring systems and anchoring types. Specific R&D efforts are focused on new turbine designs, larger rotors, taller towers, and advanced materials. The next generation of turbines will need to be larger, longer, lighter, and collectively controlled to optimise productivity and reduce maintenance costs.

Research programmes address improving component weight and costs, transport and assembly, monitoring and control, turbine reliability, grid integration, and optimising performance. Studies have shown that floating offshore wind turbines (FOWTs) can particularly benefit from increased size (upscaling) to lower the levelised cost of energy (LCOE). However, the impact of upscaling must be observed from a broader perspective (beyond capacity factors), as using longer blades that extend beyond the atmospheric boundary layer could impact turbine installation, performance, and maintenance strategies. Larger turbines will also require larger floaters, and design optimisation based on multidisciplinary integrated numerical tools is a key research topic [14]. Although not specifically designed for floating installation (see 19 2.3), the development trend of leader manufacturers is towards larger rotors, with a 15 MW machine already on the market. However, the impact of upscaling must be observed from a broader perspective.

The scientific community is actively investigating several relevant challenges, including modelling the atmosphere boundary layer, turbulence levels and oncoming flow characteristics, blade aeroelasticity, and developing advanced control systems for individual turbines and wind farms. Larger wind turbine machines will require larger floating platforms (floaters); however, scaling up existing floater designs based on scaling factors is insufficient to produce optimised designs for larger turbines. Despite the increase in mass, rotor swept area, and nacelle height inducing significant loads and overturning moments, the research highlights the benefits of larger floaters in terms of reduced platform response and lower overall costs.

The availability of experimental data and instrumentation for field tests is also a focus area, as is the need for collaboration between industry and academia to overcome intellectual property barriers and create a shared FOWT experimental database.

Design and optimisation based on multidisciplinary integrated numerical tools are also a key research topic where challenges currently being investigated are briefly outlined in the following [26] [34]:

- **Modelling the atmosphere:** the largest wind turbines now extend beyond the top of the atmospheric boundary layer and experience inflow characteristics never encountered by smaller

machines. Extreme conditions must also be considered, including hurricanes, tornadoes, microbursts, nocturnal and marine jet flows, and gravity waves. Accurate modelling of the Atmospheric Boundary Layer state is critical for designing the individual wind turbine and operational control of both turbines and integrated wind plant systems. The ability of modern computational tools to simulate specific atmospheric dynamics and configuration changes is continuously improving. Many past modelling simplifications are no longer necessary as more powerful computing facilities become available. Design criteria must evolve to include more relevant physical phenomena in a unique operating environment.

- **Modelling turbine wakes:** Wakes, or regions of slower and more turbulent air downwind of wind plants, are still not fully understood. In addition, interactions between wakes and the atmosphere dictate wind plant cost effectiveness. Furthermore, the large-scale deployment of wind farms may introduce broad impacts on local microclimates, which must be assessed. At the turbine level, rotor wake dynamics can significantly impact turbine performance as, due to wave-induced motion, the turbine's blades may face impacts with the wake, which will induce critical vibrations on the machine's mechanical components. This condition, also known as Blade Vortex Interaction, is unique to FOWT technology.
- **Modelling blade aeroelasticity:** The significant blade flexibility of larger modern turbines challenges many design assumptions and well-established performance characteristics of smaller and stiffer platforms. Blade dynamic motion and coupled aerodynamic response require comprehensive aeroelastic system design and assessment. Stability and damping criteria, if exceeded during nominal or extreme event operation, can drive nonlinear conditions that put the machine at risk and limit operability. Moreover, uncontrolled aeroelastic couplings can induce catastrophic structural failure or reduce life expectancy. The integrated dynamics of such structural design strategies require more holistic systems analysis and modelling methods, capturing both the flow physics and the nonlinear dynamic response.

Current R&D topics are moving from classical structural dynamics modelling approaches based on linear models valid for small perturbations coupled with two-dimensional aerodynamic formulations to fully 3D aeroelastic models for large displacements based on higher-fidelity Computational Fluid Dynamics solvers. Furthermore, the operating Reynolds numbers far exceed conventional wind tunnel test capabilities available worldwide, making validation of expected performance critical, especially for those conditions (e.g., post-stall angles of attack, dynamic stall, etc.) where computational fluid dynamics show the largest uncertainties. Hence, the airfoil properties and performance sensitivity to blade surface erosion, deterioration, and fouling cannot be validated, among other complexities. Consequently, greater safety margins must be used in the integrated design of a wind turbine to account for a lack of understanding and an oversimplification of its physical behaviour.

- **High performance computation and Machine learning:** The continued improvement in advanced computational capability has led to a renewed interest in Machine Learning (ML) technologies. The scientific community extensively develops mid- and high-fidelity integrated numerical tools to model a floating wind turbine's behaviour within a farm subject to complex atmospheric flows. Nevertheless, the computational costs of these solvers still represent a bottleneck for the design process. Machine Learning or Data Driven models are high-dimensional, functional approximators that can learn the nonlinear transformations between relevant inputs and outputs. They are trained on data sets obtained through experimental observations or high-fidelity simulations that

capture the dominant physical processes of interest. ML training is now an automated process, continuously updating and incorporating new data (also streaming from operational wind farms) under diverse operational conditions as the data becomes available. Hence, these models continuously evolve and improve.

- **Assessment plant modelling:** From the inflow to the manufacturing of massive parts, the size and flexibility of modern turbines have pushed design out of the territory where the design assumptions and modelling tools were first established, which creates unprecedented risks to applicability. A lack of large-scale experimental data is currently observed to validate the models and materials used to develop innovative solutions for future systems. The availability of experimental measurements is fundamental to support the validation of integrated numerical tools; hence, instrumentation capable of measuring the quantities of interest is mandatory. Instrumentation for wind tunnel testing is widely known.

Differently, instrumentation for field tests of wind turbines and plants is far less mature; hence, many R&D programmes focus on this aspect. Measurement systems will have to operate for long periods in harsh conditions. Such measurements evaluate the effects of rotor plane motion for turbines on floating platforms. Examples of measurement systems currently being studied for the installation of turbines are those related to blade surface pressure and deformation, as well as tower and blade accelerations.

- **Velocity measurement systems** such as lidar and X-band radar are being developed and tested to understand wake dynamics and intra-farm flows. Measurements of the atmosphere are also essential, as their understanding is limited at larger distances from the ground where modern turbines operate. Continued development of instruments and platforms that can carry them to larger heights includes innovative unmanned air systems and tethered balloons. In addition, measurements measuring wave properties and platform motion are fundamental.

Besides full-scale testing of prototypes or operational turbines, model-scale tests are widely adopted.

The complexity of scaling both rotor aeroelastic characteristics and floater hydrodynamic behaviour is currently being faced with the development of suitable experimental setups that effectively integrate numerical tools within an experimental facility. This is the so-called **hardware-in-the-loop (HIL) or Software-in-the-loop technique (SIL)** in which the rotor is modelled, and the floater is tested in a hydrodynamic basin or vice versa (by using a hexapod installed below a model-scale wind turbine in a wind tunnel). To be effective, these techniques require real-time running numerical tools. Hence, the use of ML techniques and HPC facilities is fundamental.

Finally, a critical aspect related to experiments and numerical tools validation is **Intellectual Property issues**, which represent a key barrier to the availability of suitable validation data for modellers. Collaboration between industry and academia is fundamental to overcoming this issue, and the design of a shared FOWT experimental database would impact the development of advanced numerical tools.

- **Developing turbine and farm advanced control systems:** Actual wind turbine control systems aim at performance optimisation and survivability of an individual turbine. Reaching the optimal power production and lowering O&M costs for a wind farm requires the design of control systems acting on the wind plant in an integrated way. As a result, highly flexible wind turbine and farm

control strategies are rapidly evolving. In detail, research on wind turbine control systems is moving toward adopting feedforward strategies that monitor and optimise rotor operations in response to changing inflow or wave conditions. Wind plant control strategies include adopting turbine-to-turbine situational awareness to actively adapt yaw and pitch in ways that alter wake interaction and maximise plant performance. The total plant production, O&M cost, and system longevity can be improved by selectively lowering a few upstream turbines' potential performance. However, the effectiveness of such a control chain relies on accurate models of how wakes impact power performance and structural loading.

- Researchers are **investigating various types of floating platforms beyond well-established options** like barges, spar buoys, semi-submersibles, and tension leg platforms. The focus of R&D efforts in this area is optimising these designs for improved stability, efficiency, and cost-effectiveness, considering specific site conditions, water depths, and environmental factors. This optimisation process involves studying the fluid-structure interaction and evaluating the choice of materials in terms of availability, recyclability, and ease of processing.

One example of a new platform concept currently under study and experimentation is the **Pendulum-stabilised platform** proposed by Saipem. This design combines the benefits of a semi-submersible (shallow draft for transport) and a spar (stability from a counterweight at depth). However, a key challenge is the complexity of the mechanisms required to lower and raise the counterweight. The platform consists of a submersible floater made of tubular elements, a counterweight connected to the floater with tendons, simple mooring lines with a drag anchor, and a lazy wave dynamic cable. The installation methodology does not require heavy-lift vessels. It is based on proven offshore installation techniques and equipment, such as anchor handling tugs, towing vessels, remotely operated vehicles, ballast chains, and subsea pressure vessels. However, the installation process is similar to that of heavy maintenance operations.

Floating substructures can be designed using steel, concrete, or both materials. The choice of materials is often made on a case-by-case basis, considering various factors. For example, Equinor utilised steel spar substructures for its 30 MW Hywind Demo project in 2017 while opting for concrete spar substructures for its 88 MW Hywind Tampen project. Several key factors influence developers' material choices:

- **Cost:** Developers meticulously assess expenses across every project stage when determining whether to use steel, concrete, or hybrid substructures. Steel generally has a lower cost per ton compared to concrete, although steel reinforcing bars are less expensive than steel plates. Steel plate prices may exhibit greater volatility, with up to 50% fluctuations within a year, whereas concrete prices tend to remain more stable. Despite reinforced concrete structures requiring significant steel, especially for reinforcement, the total steel volume is considerably lower compared to structures predominantly composed of steel.
- **Environmental impact:** Environmental factors heavily influence developers' decisions and are often included as decision criteria in competitive offtake auctions. The carbon footprint is contingent upon the manufacturing processes of steel and cement, operational lifespan, and recycling or reuse options at the end of the structure's life cycle. Steel is frequently recycled, while concrete is usually crushed and reused. Lifecycle analysis proves to be an invaluable tool for evaluating such considerations.

- **Supply chain and local content:** Concrete fabrication may be simpler in regions with no established steel fabrication supply chain and entail less investment in new facilities. Localising concrete fabrication can create more employment opportunities than steel fabrication. Nevertheless, it is important to consider the jobs associated with steel and cement manufacturing. Concrete substructures are heavier than steel, necessitating more work for lifting or towing and deeper channels if transportation is required.
- **Site condition:** Metocean conditions can also impact the choice of materials due to the varying performance characteristics of different materials over time. For example, concrete substructures may be more vulnerable to freeze-thaw damage, whereas steel foundations may be more susceptible to corrosion.

Other R&D topics related to the durability of the floating platform include novel methods for vibration suppression and dampening and hybridisation with wind-wave platforms, which can act as shock absorbers for the platform.

Regarding supply logistics, R&D activities are mostly focused on developing and optimising specialised vessels to improve the transport and installation of FOWTs. Recently, a Norwegian company's 'WindSpider' project has revolutionised offshore wind turbine installation and maintenance. It uses an aluminium crane that clings to towers, reducing relative movement between the crane and turbine and allowing operations in strong winds. This innovation is expected to significantly reduce lifecycle costs and enhance efficiency in the sector, enabling on-site, cost-saving component replacements without needing towing back and streamlining wind turbine installations from various locations. Designed for scalability, WindSpider can handle lifts over 1500 tonnes without height limitations. It ensures rapid mobilisation and demobilisation, improves operability under windy conditions, and reduces the necessity for quayside upgrades. Compatible with existing vessels and barges, it has shown promising results across several floating design concepts without requiring wind turbine or tower modifications. Integrating with the turbine structure effectively addresses the challenge of relative motion during operations. Its modular design enhances transportability by road or sea, marking a significant advancement in offshore wind technology [35] [36].

The continued research and development of innovative, dynamic electrical infrastructure is crucial for the widespread adoption of the FOWT sector. This includes innovations in cable conductor core types and materials to minimise losses and exploration of fatigue-resistant materials and designs to prevent water ingress, which can be used instead of lead sheaths.

Breakaway designs are being developed to allow decoupling at a given load following platform drift-off, protecting the rest of the electrical system. However, these breakaway connectors currently have a low Technology Readiness Level (TRL), and their use in floating offshore applications is yet to be thoroughly understood for floating offshore applications [37].

Current high-voltage gas-insulated switchgear (HVGIS) certified for offshore operations is unsuitable for floating offshore applications. The HVGIS was designed to counter seismic motions, not the larger amplitude and higher-frequency motions experienced on a floating offshore substation.

To accelerate the progression of FOWT projects, transparency and knowledge sharing between developers should be actively encouraged to close feedback loops rapidly and reduce the timeline for innovations to reach a high TRL.

While effective in securing platforms to the seabed, traditional mooring systems often lack versatility and adaptability. Fixed mooring solutions are typically designed for specific conditions and do not easily accommodate changes in environmental forces, seabed conditions, or operational requirements. This is where innovative, adaptable mooring equipment comes into play, offering enhanced flexibility and efficiency that were previously unattainable. The core of this innovation lies in integrating advanced materials, smart design, and technology. High-performance synthetic materials offer unprecedented strength-to-weight ratios and resistance to harsh marine environments. Incorporating smart sensors and IoT technology enables real-time monitoring and adjustment of mooring tensions. This adaptability ensures optimal performance across a wide range of conditions, reducing the risk of failure and extending the lifespan of the mooring system.

As floating structures operate at increasing depths, traditional mooring systems, such as high-weight anchor chains and steel cables, face limitations in meeting the demands of deepwater operations. Chains' weight rapidly increases, resulting in greater tension and vertical load on the structure, reducing the useful load capacity. Additionally, the effectiveness of chain mooring systems decreases rapidly with increasing water depth. To address these challenges, deepwater operations often rely on tensioned mooring systems, which maintain tension by applying pre-tension to both cable sides. Tensioned mooring, an innovative mooring system for deepwater platforms, employs a combination of materials like chain-polyester-chain to address the challenges of deep waters. Its compact mooring radius, low total weight, and corrosion resistance have gained widespread adoption.

- **Synthetic fibre ropes in tensioned mooring:** Synthetic fibre ropes, including PET¹, HMPE², and Aramid³, are commonly used in tensioned mooring systems due to their favourable strength-to-mass ratio, low axial stiffness for rope elongation, shorter mooring lines reducing the system's footprint, and higher restoring forces reducing platform displacement. The widespread application of tensioned mooring systems on deepwater drilling platforms has underscored the importance of synthetic fibre ropes in mooring system research.
- **Anchoring differences:** A significant distinction between chain mooring and tensioned leg mooring lies in the behaviour of the anchoring point. While a chain mooring aligns horizontally once it reaches the seabed, a tensioned leg mooring arrives at an angle, requiring the anchoring point to resist horizontal and vertical forces. In chain mooring, restoring forces derive from the weight of the mooring line, while in tensioned leg mooring, reliance is placed on the elasticity of the mooring line and dampers to limit rope tears and wear.

¹ PET — Polyester ropes as strong as nylon when dry and retain their strength when wet.

² HMPE—High Modulus Polyethylene: This is polyethylene that is much stronger and stiffer than regular polyethylene, also known as Spectra and Dyneema.

³ Aramid high modulus fibre, also known as Kevlar and Twaron. Aramid fibres are high-temperature-resistant and have been developed for various high-performance applications.

2.7. Standardisation, Compliance and Certification

The key aspects of accelerating floating offshore wind deployment are the need for standardisation, compliance, and certification:

- **Standardisation:** The development of new international standards specifically for floating offshore wind turbines, including standards for design, construction, operation, and maintenance. This is being led by the IEC TC 88/PT 61400-3-2 subcommittee. Incorporating weather and natural conditions from new offshore wind markets beyond Europe into the international standards (e.g. DNV) is needed to ensure they are applicable globally. The support for international standards-making bodies to keep up with the rapid pace of the floating offshore wind industry [38] [39] [40]. An example is the standardisation of FOWT designs, which is crucial to enable collaboration between manufacturers due to the technical complexity and intellectual property challenges in FOWT designs.
- **Compliance and certification:** Increased role of classification societies in certifying the design, construction, installation, and operations of floating wind structures and components to ensure safety, reliability, and performance. Certification services provided by classification societies, such as Approval in Principle (AiP) and Basic Design Approval (BDA), help prove new floating wind technologies and reduce investment risk. Risk management assessments by classification societies help developers, investors, and operators assess and manage the risks of floating offshore wind projects. Certification of floating wind projects and components to established international standards, such as the IEC 61400 series, to build investor confidence. Some examples:
 - I. **Certification of dynamic electrical infrastructure** for FOWT (dynamic cables, connectors, switch gear). Certification of designs poses a further challenge; for example, to date, no high voltage dynamic cable (HVDC) designs are certified, the highest being up to 66 kV. There is a certified HV switch gear. Connectors are certified for use in the oil and gas industry but not FOWF.
 - II. **Certification and compliance of components:** In the broader sense, modularity and standardisation of components will ease global supply chain saturation and spare part availability. Standardisation and certification of turbine and platform configuration will ease the transport of FOWT and platforms to sites, as well as standardisation and certification of vessels for the transportation of FOWT. Certification of mooring and anchoring ropes and systems by a specialist body enables confidence in new designs and materials.

Standardisation of FOWT designs and components can reduce the high technical skills required, making training and deploying a larger workforce across developments easier. Hence, comprehensive standardisation, compliance, and certification frameworks are essential to address the unique technical challenges, supply chain barriers, and skills gaps hindering the rapid deployment of floating offshore wind technology.

2.8. Electricity Networks, Grid Connectivity and Flexibility

Integrating floating offshore wind farms into the wider energy system poses one of the greatest challenges to the technology. A supportive grid must be developed at the same rate as growth in wind farm capacity

to maximise the production of useable energy and reduce the risk of wind turbine curtailment. The high-voltage DC transmission network constraints, particularly at the interface between Scotland and England, result in significant revenue losses for electricity providers.

- I. **Adopting whole systems** can mitigate these approaches to wind farm development given the wider grid network and the Holistic Network Design (HND) implementation to enable the optimised transmission of offshore-generated renewables.
- II. **The Holistic Network Design (HND)** will alleviate these bottlenecks by strengthening the offshore and onshore cabling network and strategic positioning of HV substations at critical connection points for onshore and offshore infrastructure. This has been forecast to reduce constraint costs by £13.1 billion. However, the duration and financial expense of grid strengthening means the fundamental need for a government commitment to offshore renewables and floating offshore wind farms underlines the HND [41].
- III. **Longer term Government energy forecasts** are needed outlining the intended build capacity over the next 25 years, contrasting the short term leasing rounds, which are the current status quo. A longer term government commitment to floating offshore wind will increase confidence and foster investment in the technology, and as such, will encourage the strategised, holistic grid development to support offshore assets. As the owners of the maritime areas, the Crown Estate and the Crown Estate Scotland have an obligation to consider the required infrastructure to support floating offshore wind developments when leasing the seabed to these projects. The requirements should be considered in the early stages of the consenting process to allow for a systematic deployment of offshore and onshore wind farms and grid-side infrastructure.

Floating offshore wind farms can be located in areas with much higher wind resources previously inaccessible to fixed bottom turbines. The greater distance from the shore is a challenge for the transmission of generated electricity to the onshore substations due to the increased cable length, resulting in greater voltage drops and thermal losses. This technical challenge is complicated by the nature of floating offshore wind, which necessitates dynamic electrical infrastructure where dynamic cables, specialised connectors, protectors, and other ancillary equipment are critical components in FOWF. These components represent single points of failure for a turbine if faults occur in the inter-array cabling, or more critically, for the entire wind farm, in the advent of failure with the export cable.

- I. **Dynamic export cables**, connecting the floating offshore sub-station to the static cable, are a critical failure point for the entire wind farm and thus require over engineering to mitigate potential. The dynamic cables must be able to accommodate the extreme displacements that the floating offshore wind substations will encounter during a storm and have the fatigue stability to endure 20 years of service, whilst the choice of connector (wet-mate, dry-mate or break-away) connectors depends on the maintenance strategy.
- II. **Breakaway designs**: Presently, break-away connectors have a low TRL, and their use is yet to be thoroughly understood for floating offshore applications. The continuation of research and development into innovative, dynamic electrical infrastructure is imperative for the uptake of the FOW sector; this includes innovations into cable conductor core types and materials to minimise losses and exploration of fatigue resistant materials and designs to prevent water ingress that can be used in place of lead sheaths [37].

To accelerate the progression of FOW projects, transparency and knowledge sharing between developers should be actively encouraged to close feedback loops rapidly and reduce the timeline for innovations to reach a high TRL. From then, the standardisation and certification of the dynamic electrical infrastructure and high voltage switchgear will enable the advanced manufacturing and deployment of floating offshore wind components.

Hybridising wind energy with other renewables like floating solar and wave energy can mitigate power output variability, enhancing revenue from offshore wind projects. Floating offshore wind technology enables exploration of high wave resource areas, overcoming water depth limitations. Synchronised with wind peaks, wave energy aligns well with floating offshore wind. Co-sharing maritime space between floating offshore wind turbines (FOWT) and wave energy converters (WEC) presents a commercialisation opportunity, reducing costs through shared infrastructure and operations. This collaboration, especially with versatile platforms, could cut LCOE by 7% for wind and 40% for wave projects. Similar opportunities exist with floating solar, albeit in the R&D phase [42].

Hybridising FOWTs with hydrogen storage presents a significant opportunity to enhance the generation profile. The system gains flexibility and mitigates variability by storing surplus electricity as hydrogen. This approach alleviates grid constraints, eliminates the necessity for curtailing FOW output, and ensures generation during low-wind periods. The potential impact includes reducing the Levelised Cost of Energy (LCOE) for floating offshore wind farms, thereby increasing returns for developers. Pilot projects are underway to explore and implement this innovative solution.

2.9. Non-Technological barriers and enablers

The key non-technological barriers highlighted below are related to legal, political, environmental, and social factors. At the same time, the enablers involve creating supportive policy and regulatory environments, engaging stakeholders, and leveraging digital technologies and innovation.

2.9.1. Regulatory and permitting challenges

Regulatory and permitting challenges are significant barriers to deploying floating offshore wind turbine farms. As floating wind technology is relatively new and less mature than bottom-fixed offshore wind farms, the regulatory environment and permitting processes may not be fully developed or adapted to accommodate the unique aspects of floating wind projects [43]. Key challenges include:

- **Lack of established regulatory framework:** In some jurisdictions, floating offshore wind farms may lack a well-defined regulatory framework, leading to uncertainty and delays in the permitting process. Policymakers and regulators must develop clear guidelines and standards tailored to floating wind projects' specific requirements and challenges to facilitate their successful deployment.
- **Complex permitting process:** The permitting process for floating wind projects can be complex, involving multiple agencies and jurisdictions at the local, regional, and national levels. This complexity can lead to lengthy timelines, increased costs, and uncertainty for project developers. Streamlining the permitting process and coordinating efforts between relevant authorities can help address these challenges.
- **Environmental regulations:** Floating wind farms must comply with various environmental regulations and standards to protect marine ecosystems, birds, and other wildlife. The

permitting process may require comprehensive environmental impact assessments (EIAs), which can be time-consuming and costly. Developing clear guidelines for conducting EIAs and ensuring proper consultation with relevant stakeholders can help minimise delays and improve the permitting process [43].

- **Stakeholder engagement:** Engaging with local communities, environmental groups, and other stakeholders is essential during the permitting process to address concerns, share information, and build public support for floating wind projects. However, this can be challenging, particularly if there is a limited understanding of the technology or concerns about potential impacts on the environment, tourism, or other industries.
- **Site selection and lease agreements:** Securing suitable sites for floating wind farms can be challenging, as it involves identifying appropriate areas with favourable wind resources, water depths, and environmental conditions. In addition, developers must negotiate lease agreements with relevant authorities, which can be a complex and lengthy process.
- **Grid connection and power purchase agreements:** Obtaining permits for grid connection and negotiating power purchase agreements (PPAs) with utilities or other off takers can be challenging for floating wind projects. These processes involve navigating complex regulations, technical requirements, and market conditions, which can impact the project's overall financial viability.

2.9.2. Environmental Impact

Environmental impacts associated with floating offshore wind farms are crucial during their planning, construction, and operation phases. While these wind farms can help reduce greenhouse gas emissions by producing clean energy, it is essential to identify and mitigate potential adverse effects on the environment. Key environmental impacts to consider include:

- **Marine Ecosystems:** Floating wind farms may impact marine ecosystems through construction noise, potentially disturbing marine mammals, and fish. Additionally, the installation may create artificial habitats, altering local biodiversity. Comprehensive environmental assessments, careful site and design selection, and adaptive management during operation are crucial to mitigate these impacts. Ongoing research projects contribute to reducing the environmental footprint of offshore wind farms [44].
- **Birds and Avian Species:** Floating wind farms pose risks to birds and avian species, including collision with turbine blades and disturbance of nesting or feeding areas. Mitigating these impacts requires careful site selection, monitoring, and proper management. Pre-construction studies, bird-friendly turbine designs, and ongoing research into bird behaviour and deterrent systems contribute to effective mitigation strategies [45] [46].
- **Benthic Habitats:** The installation of mooring and anchoring systems for floating wind farms can disrupt benthic habitats and seabed, causing localised changes to the seafloor and benthic communities. To minimise these impacts, efforts include optimising mooring designs, selecting appropriate anchoring systems, and conducting thorough environmental assessments. Preserving benthic habitats involves minimising the physical footprint through careful site selection, innovative mooring designs, sensitive construction scheduling, and optimised cable routing. Ongoing research explores advanced technologies and strategies to reduce these impacts further.
- **Noise Impacts:** Floating offshore wind farms can affect coastal communities and marine users visually and acoustically. However, these impacts are generally less significant than those from

nearshore bottom-fixed wind farms. Addressing these issues in planning and design involves implementing sound dampening techniques. Ongoing research aims to enhance turbine designs and layouts to minimise visual impacts and develop effective noise reduction methods for protecting marine life and coastal communities [47].

- **Electromagnetic Fields (EMF):** Subsea power cables generate electromagnetic fields (EMF), potentially impacting marine species, especially those relying on natural geomagnetic fields for navigation, such as sharks and rays. Minimising these effects involves proper cable routing, shielding, and burial. Effective mitigation strategies, including improved understanding and research, are being explored to ensure minimal disturbance to marine life.
- **Cumulative Impacts:** In regions where multiple offshore wind projects are planned or already in operation, the cumulative environmental impacts may be more significant than those from a single project.

2.9.3. Public acceptance

Public acceptance is an essential factor for the successful deployment of floating offshore wind turbine farms. Gaining support from local communities, stakeholders, and the wider public is crucial to ensure the smooth development and operation of these projects [48].

Key aspects to consider when addressing public acceptance include:

- **Environmental concerns:** Floating wind farms may raise concerns about potential impacts on marine ecosystems, bird populations, and other wildlife. Transparently communicating the results of environmental impact assessments and demonstrating how potential impacts will be mitigated can help alleviate these concerns and build trust with the public.
- **Visual impact:** Floating wind farms located close to shorelines may generate concerns about visual impacts on coastal landscapes and potential effects on tourism. Selecting appropriate sites with minimal visual impact, considering the use of innovative designs that blend into the environment, and engaging with local communities to address these concerns can help improve public acceptance.
- **Noise and vibrations:** Noise and vibrations from the construction and operation of floating wind farms can be a concern for nearby communities, particularly those near the shore. Implementing noise reduction measures, such as low-noise construction techniques, and providing accurate information about the expected noise levels can help address these concerns.
- **Socio-economic benefits:** Highlighting the potential socio-economic benefits of floating offshore wind projects, such as job creation, local economic development, and increased energy security, can help build public support. Engaging with local communities, businesses, and stakeholders to maximise local content and ensure equitable distribution of benefits can further enhance public acceptance.
- **Education and awareness:** Raising awareness and understanding of floating offshore wind technology, its benefits, and its potential role in meeting climate and energy goals can help build

public support. This can involve organising public information sessions, workshops, and site visits and collaborating with educational institutions to include floating wind topics in their curricula.

- **Stakeholder engagement:** Engaging with local communities, environmental groups, and other stakeholders throughout the project development process is essential to address concerns, share information, and build public support. Establishing open lines of communication, involving stakeholders in decision-making processes, and being responsive to feedback can help foster trust and promote acceptance of floating wind projects.
- **Transparent decision-making:** Ensuring transparent decision-making processes and providing clear information about project planning, permitting, and environmental assessments can help build trust and credibility with the public. This involves making project documents and data easily accessible, providing regular updates on project progress, and being open about the potential risks and uncertainties associated with the project.

2.9.4. Supporting Market signals, Regulations, and systems coordination

- **Clear Industrial Strategy and manufacturing support** are required to attract local manufacturing opportunities for the UK to capitalise on growth within the sector. This will reduce dependency on imports, ease global supply chain constraints, and increase profitability for the local economy.
- **Early consultation and commitment to ports:** Ports are key players in the successful wide scale deployment of FOWF. Early consultation and commitment to ports will enable the timely development of port infrastructure to match the demand for wind farm development.
- **Long term commitment:** Government commitment to the development plan for the intended wind farm capacity will encourage the building of crucial infrastructure as returns are more guaranteed.
- **Adequate funding and investment support:** Ports incur significant CapEx without guaranteeing wind farm businesses. Funding allocations can be used for ports to implement high-expense activities associated with FOWF installation vessels, such as dredging and increasing birthing depth. Subsidies and investments can also be used to encourage the development of specialised vehicles to transport WTG to sites.
- **Electricity and Network:** Long-term energy strategy outlined by the Government to confirm the position that offshore wind and FOW will play in the future energy system. A 25-year government plan for offshore wind's planned installed capacity (GW) will enable coordination between multiple actors to deliver whole systems. This will motivate the supply chain to build the **necessary key infrastructure for grid strengthening and development, and the UK as the supply chain (building of ports, training) will** also motivate manufacturers to invest in the UK market. – Confidence in the returns and position as a fundamental technology for achieving net zero.

2.10. Summary of key enablers

2.10.1. Technological Enablers

Platform Design and Stability: Research efforts are ongoing to optimise the design and performance of FOWT platforms using numerical simulations, physical testing, and full-scale demonstrations. For

example, the European Commission-funded LIFES50+ project is developing a multi-purpose floating platform for offshore wind and ocean energy based on a semi-submersible design. The project aims to address the technical challenges facing the deployment of FOWTs, such as platform stability, mooring system design, and wind turbine performance, as well as the need for more cost-effective and sustainable solutions for the renewable energy industry [49].

Mooring and Anchoring Systems: Research efforts are ongoing to optimise the design and performance of FOWT mooring and anchoring systems using numerical simulations, physical testing, and full-scale demonstrations. For example, the ECO2FOW project is developing an eco-design and eco-innovation framework for FOWT mooring systems based on a hybrid mooring system that combines the advantages of single-point and multi-point mooring systems. The project aims to address the technical and environmental challenges facing the deployment of FOWTs, such as reducing the environmental impact of the mooring system on the seabed and improving the efficiency and cost-effectiveness of the system [50].

Wind Turbine Performance: Research efforts are ongoing to optimise the design and performance of FOWT wind turbines using numerical simulations, physical testing, and full-scale demonstrations. For example, the FLOTANT project develops a novel floating wind turbine system based on a TLP platform and a downwind rotor. The project aims to improve the energy yield and reduce the cost of FOWTs by optimising the turbine design and control systems and reducing the system's environmental impact [51].

Operation and Maintenance: Research efforts are ongoing to develop more efficient and cost-effective operation and maintenance strategies for FOWTs, using advanced monitoring and control systems, predictive maintenance techniques, and autonomous inspection and repair systems. For example, the EU-funded DTOceanPlus project is developing a software tool for the planning and optimisation of offshore renewable energy systems, including FOWTs, to improve the efficiency and reliability of the operation and maintenance process [52] [53].

2.10.2. Financial enablers:

To overcome these financing challenges, the following measures can be considered:

Public funding and support: Government-backed loans, grants, or incentives can help reduce the risks associated with floating wind projects and attract private investment. Public funding can also support research and development efforts to advance technology and reduce costs.

Demonstrating successful pilot projects: By showcasing successful pilot or demonstration projects, the industry can provide valuable data on the performance, reliability, and cost-effectiveness of floating wind technology, helping to build investor confidence.

Collaboration and risk-sharing: Collaboration between industry stakeholders, including developers, manufacturers, and investors, can help distribute risks and pool resources. Joint ventures or partnerships can facilitate knowledge sharing and reduce individual investors' risk exposure.

Developing a supportive regulatory framework: Clear and supportive regulatory frameworks can create a more predictable investment environment for floating wind projects, reducing risks and uncertainties for investors.

2.10.3. Environmental Impacts

To mitigate these environmental impacts, several measures can be taken, such as:

Thorough environmental impact assessments (EIAs): Conducting comprehensive environmental impact assessments (EIAs) is vital to identifying, evaluating, and mitigating potential environmental risks associated with floating offshore wind farms. EIAs inform the decision-making process, helping to minimise adverse impacts and ensure compliance with environmental regulations.

Site selection: Careful site selection can help avoid or minimise impacts on sensitive habitats, marine protected areas, or important bird areas, reducing potential environmental risks.

Monitoring and adaptive management: Implementing monitoring programs during construction and operation can help identify potential impacts and inform adaptive management strategies, allowing for adjustments to minimise environmental risks.

Stakeholder engagement: Engaging with local communities, regulators, and other stakeholders is essential to addressing concerns, sharing information, and developing collaborative solutions to mitigate environmental impacts.

Best practices and guidelines: Following established practices and guidelines for the design, construction, and operation of floating offshore wind farms can help minimise environmental impacts and promote the responsible development of this renewable energy source.

2.10.4. Regulatory and Permitting

To address these regulatory and permitting challenges, policymakers, regulators, and industry stakeholders can work together to:

Develop a supportive regulatory framework: Creating clear and supportive regulatory frameworks for floating offshore wind projects can reduce risks and uncertainties for developers, investors, and other stakeholders, facilitating the successful deployment of floating wind farms.

Streamline permitting processes: Simplifying and coordinating the permitting process across relevant agencies and jurisdictions can help minimise delays, reduce costs, and improve the overall efficiency of project development.

Enhance stakeholder engagement: Establishing open lines of communication and engaging with local communities, environmental groups, and other stakeholders can help build public support, address concerns, and promote the responsible development of floating wind projects.

Foster collaboration: Encouraging collaboration between industry stakeholders, policymakers, regulators, and research institutions can help share knowledge, identify best practices, and develop innovative solutions to regulatory and permitting challenges.

3. SYSTEMS INTEGRATION BARRIERS AND ENABLERS

Integrating floating offshore wind farms into the existing power grid presents several key challenges that must be addressed to ensure this renewable energy technology's successful deployment and integration. One of the primary barriers is the variable and intermittent nature of the power generated by floating offshore wind farms. The fluctuations in wind speed can lead to instability and reliability issues within the power grid, requiring advanced grid management techniques, power electronics, and energy storage solutions to maintain grid stability and optimise wind energy utilisation.

Another challenge is the grid connection and infrastructure required to transmit the power generated by floating offshore wind farms to the onshore grid. Developing the necessary submarine export cables and grid infrastructure can be complex and costly, particularly as wind farms are farther from the shore. Strategies such as using high-voltage direct current (HVDC) transmission, shared transmission systems, and offshore energy islands can help address these challenges.

Technological advancements and cost competitiveness are also critical barriers that must be overcome. Floating wind technology is relatively new, and continued research and development efforts are required to enhance its efficiency, durability, and cost-effectiveness. Achieving economies of scale and streamlining regulatory frameworks will drive down costs and accelerate the adoption of floating offshore wind.

Finally, integrating floating offshore wind farms must minimise environmental and social impacts. Careful siting, routing, and protection of the necessary infrastructure, as well as collaboration with local stakeholders, are crucial to ensuring the sustainable development of this renewable energy resource. The integration of floating offshore wind can be optimised by addressing these key barriers and leveraging the various enablers, such as advanced grid management techniques, hybrid energy systems, and innovative transmission solutions.

The characteristics of offshore wind farms, particularly floating wind farms, and their geographical distribution can amplify the significance of certain issues or introduce new ones. This chapter analyses the primary barriers and enablers for integrating future floating wind farms into the grid and the energy system. The future energy system will be more interconnected than the present one, making it more challenging to categorise these barriers and enablers strictly. The chapter will present a tentative grouping of these factors:

- Grid integration and flexibility (Section 5.1).
- Hybrid Systems (Section 5.3).
- Energy storage (Section 5.4).

4. LASTLY, SOME CASE STUDIES ABOUT THE ABOVE-LISTED TOPICS ARE REPORTED IN

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ANNEX to better understand the expected barriers and/or benefits.

5.1. Characteristics of floating offshore Wind farms

Floating offshore wind farms are a rapidly evolving technology that offers several unique characteristics compared to traditional fixed-bottom offshore wind farms. The main characteristics of floating offshore wind farms that could affect system integration are listed below:

- **Deeper Water Accessibility:** Unlike fixed-bottom offshore wind turbines, floating wind turbines are not limited to shallow coastal waters. They can be deployed in deeper waters, often 60 meters or more, opening vast new areas for wind energy development. However, the distance to shore is high, particularly in regions like the Mediterranean Sea, where coastal tourism is well-developed, so the visual impact needs to be minimised.
- **Reduced Environmental Impact:** Floating wind farms have a smaller seabed footprint than fixed-bottom designs, minimising the disturbance to marine ecosystems during installation and operation.
- **Increased Flexibility:** Floating platforms can be towed to the installation site, allowing easier transportation and deployment in remote or hard-to-access locations.

- Scalability: Floating wind farms can be scaled up more easily than fixed-bottom designs, as the floating platforms can accommodate larger and more powerful turbines.
- Adaptability: Floating wind farms can be relocated or decommissioned more easily than fixed-bottom designs, providing greater flexibility in response to changing environmental or economic conditions.
- Technological Innovation: Floating wind technology is still relatively new, offering opportunities for continued research and development to improve efficiency, reliability, and cost-effectiveness.
- Other considerations:
 - Offshore wind farms, especially floating ones, are generally larger in scale compared to onshore wind farms. Many onshore wind farms already operate in many countries, leading to a shortage of available land and decreasing social acceptance.
 - After a certain distance from shore (around 50 km for a 1 GW floating offshore wind farm), DC export cables become more convenient than AC cables [54].
 - The first areas for floating wind deployment are expected to be the windiest offshore regions located close to shore.
 - The deployment of large amounts of offshore wind energy will supplement the existing onshore renewable energy production.
 - Wind and solar energy, as variable renewable energy (VRE) sources, will provide most of the new renewable capacity installed in the coming decades.

In the next section, a closer examination of the situation in Italy provides more clarity and context around some of the earlier points made by delving deeper into the specifics of the Italian context to better understand and expand upon the previous assertions.

5.1.1. Focus on Italy

The Italian Wind Atlas AEOLIAN indicates that the southern regions of Italy, particularly Sicily and Sardinia, have a higher wind resource potential than the country's northern parts. The mean annual wind speed map shows stronger and more consistent winds in the southern regions, suggesting greater opportunities for both onshore and offshore wind energy development, as shown in the mean annual mean speed map from the Italian Wind Atlas AEOLIAN reported in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Mean annual wind speed @ 100 m a.g.l./a.s.l. [55] .

As expected, most of the installed wind capacity is located in the Southern Regions, Apulian, Campania, Basilicata, and Calabria Region, as well as in the main islands of Sicily and Sardinia Region. In Figure 4, the map of the regional percentage of the total capacity installed in Italy at the end of 2023, 12,1 GW, is reported together with the administrative Region map.

Figure 4: The regional distribution (%) of the cumulative on-land wind energy installed capacity in 2023 (left) and the Italian region map (right).

In addition to this capacity, many photovoltaic (PV) installations already exist in Italy: a cumulative PV capacity of more than 28 GW was in operation at the end of 2023.

According to the National Integrated Climate and Energy Plan (NECP), the total increment of renewable production in 2030 will be given by wind and solar technologies, see Figure 5. The green line representing Wind Energy production shows a 2030 target of around two times the present one, and the yellow line representing PV production shows a 2030 target of around three times the present one. In total, an addition of VRE production slightly lower than 100 TWh is expected in 2030.

Figure 5: Expected trend of RES installed capacity (TWh) increase to meet Italian NECP 2030 targets [56].

The new RES capacity needed to reach the 2030 production target is expected to be still concentrated in the Southern Regions and main islands, as confirmed by the map of new grid connection requests

reported in Figure 6. In these areas, grid reinforcement and new grid connections, such as the new offshore Tyrrhenian link, shown in Figure 7 are planned by the Italian Transmission System Operator Terna.

Figure 6: Map of new RES grid connection requests as of 31st December 2023 (source Terna [57]): PV plants are yellow, onshore wind plants are green, and offshore wind plants are blue.

Figure 7 Tyrrhenian link (source Terna [58]).

Even if all the planned grid reinforcements are realised quickly, and the grid is ready to transmit a large amount of floating offshore wind production, some grid congestion and intrinsic grid issues will rise with the increase in wind production. The following section provides more details.

5.2. Grid Integration and Flexibility

The role of offshore wind, including floating wind turbines, in supporting grid flexibility is crucial in enhancing the resilience and adaptability of the power grid. While integrating floating wind turbines presents technical, operational, and regulatory challenges, the benefits in terms of flexibility and resilience are significant. The variability and intermittency of wind energy, influenced by varying wind speeds and unpredictable weather events, require innovative solutions for whole integration into the grid.

Grid operators must balance supply and demand in real time to maintain stability without causing blackouts due to the variability of wind energy. Surplus electricity generated during optimal wind conditions needs efficient management to prevent wastage. Upgrades to grid infrastructure may be necessary to accommodate increased capacity from wind farms, while regulatory frameworks should ensure fair compensation for operators and incentivise further renewable energy investments.

Despite these challenges, integrating wind farms into the grid offers substantial flexibility, contributing to a reliable and sustainable electricity supply. Leveraging advanced technologies and innovative strategies can enhance grid stability, efficiency, and resilience. Ensuring energy integration with the required capacity and flexibility is a key priority for driving progress in the sector [59].

As can be easily understood, the challenges of wind integration in the power system are not a matter of a single technology but a multidimensional problem. The main issues raised by the increase of wind (and PV) technologies in the power system are the variability of operation and the connection through non-synchronous machines [60].

One of the most challenging constraints on the power system is maintaining the continuous balance between production and demand. This balance is still managed in most countries with conventional fossil-fuel power plants. However, some additional/substituting solutions must be found to fulfil the requirement of a reliable power supply at acceptable costs in a future Net Zero System when fossil fuel capacity is dramatically reduced.

A specific research Task about “Design and Operation of Energy Systems with Large Amounts of Variable Generation” is active in the frame of the IEA Wind Energy TCP [60]. Some results about the strategies for continuous balancing of future power systems with high wind and solar shares have been recently published in Nordström [61]. The analysis in different geographical areas shows that the challenges and the solutions adopted in power systems depend significantly on the size of the system, its interconnections, and the time scale at which the balance is managed.

Different services are contributing to continuous balancing in the grid. In Figure 8, these services are shown together with their typical time scale.

FRR: Frequency Restoration Reserves
 RP: Ramping Products
 RR: Replacement Reserves

Figure 8 Approximate timeframes of different balancing services [61].

One common trend is involving more technologies (grid, generation, and storage technologies) for balancing, especially for systems historically based on fossil-fuel generation.

Concerning grid technologies, most present power grids are characterised by a high share of generation plants (fossil fuel, nuclear and hydro) interconnected through synchronous machines (so-called grid-following) that can manage the inertia of the system and give other services to compensate for the mismatch between production and consumption. A paradigm change is needed with an increasing share of plants with non-synchronous machines, such as wind and solar. For example, a new class of inverter-based resource controls (so-called grid-forming), able to inject active power to compensate for a mismatch with low frequency change, together with synchronous condensers, will be able to manage grid with around 100% amounts of non-synchronous generation [62].

Wind technology is already able to provide frequency and voltage control under proper technological and system conditions [63]. However, they could impact the revenue of the wind plants.

Many research and development activities are required to develop wind technologies (i.e. single turbine control, wind park control) and grid technologies, i.e. (inverter-based technologies, HVDC technologies), as well as communication and digitalisation and communication technologies. Storage systems could make another contribution to energy balancing. The features of the available storage technologies are summarised in Figure 9.

Source: School of Engineering, RMIT University (2015)

Figure 9: Main Feature of storage technologies (Wikipedia).

A focus on the coupling of floating offshore wind technology and storage systems is reported in Section 5.4.

Ancillary services

Offshore wind power has gained traction due to its vast untapped potential, offering strong and consistent winds for efficient energy production.

Demand side response: In grid congestions, wind farm owners are often asked to decrease or stop production, leading to curtailments. To address this, a combination of multiple renewable technologies with different variability profiles can be aggregated into a hybrid system to smooth the variability of wind energy production and compensate for the daily fluctuations of solar PV generation [64]. This hybrid system approach is particularly suitable for offshore applications, where there is ample space among the wind turbines in a wind farm. This is discussed in detail in Section 5.3.

Demand-side flexibility can also contribute to energy balancing, such as using more flexible loads or grid services like vehicle-to-grid (V2G) options [65].

Economic considerations: Ultimately, all these solutions must achieve economic sustainability. The costs of integrating high percentages of wind energy into different power systems must be assessed. At the same time, the services that wind farms can provide to the power system should be properly remunerated.

Policy considerations: According to the European Wind Energy Association, "all future considerations by policymakers on balancing responsibilities by wind power generators need to take into account market maturity as well as the penetration level of wind power in the respective power system." Ensuring fair compensation for the valuable grid services provided by wind farms is crucial for the long-term economic viability of high-renewable energy systems [66]. According to the European Wind Energy Association, "*all future considerations by policymakers on balancing responsibilities by wind power generators need to take into account market maturity as well as the penetration level of wind power in the respective power system*" [67].

5.3. Hybrid Systems

As mentioned before, in recent years, floating wind farms have started to develop and demonstrate the potential for large-scale deployment. Expanding the adoption of floating wind energy offers clear advantages but also comes with several challenges, as previously discussed. Issues include production variability, relatively higher costs, potential interference with other offshore activities, and public acceptance of installations. Another challenge floating offshore wind and ocean energy systems encounter is the possibility of overproduction. Since offshore wind farms tend to be situated in the windiest areas, despite efforts to strengthen onshore grids, they may struggle to handle all the energy generated offshore, resulting in production curtailment.

To date, there have been notable advancements and innovations aimed at improving turbine efficiency, stability, and scalability. Combining floating wind energy with other offshore renewables on the same platform (hybrid platform) and/or in the same area (co-location) can mitigate some barriers to offshore renewable deployment by decreasing the conflict with other activities and increasing acceptability. In addition, combining the production from renewables with different variability can increase the flexibility and the quality of the overall power supply and facilitate grid integration. Note that energy system flexibility is defined here as the ability to adjust supply and demand to achieve that energy balance, keeping energy flow through the networks within safe limits, and grid balancing continuously matches supply the supply-to-demand of the Energy systems. The share of some infrastructures (such as ports,

grid, etc.) can contribute to decreasing costs. At the same time, combining devices of different maturities can accelerate the development of less advanced ones.

The variability of renewable generation, especially wind power, poses a substantial challenge for the grid. When renewable energy cannot be transported to the final consumer due to network constraints, carbon-intensive gas generation typically needs to be turned up to compensate, resulting in higher carbon emissions and consumer costs. In the UK, for instance, in 2020, wind generation curtailment reached 3.5TWh due to system constraints, decreasing to 2.3TWh in 2021 due to low wind levels and post-Covid demand recovery. This curtailed wind generation could have powered 800,000 homes annually over the two years. Wind curtailment cost Great Britain consumers £299m in 2020 and surged to £507m in 2021, primarily due to high gas prices toward the end of 2021, resulting in over £200m in costs in November alone. Figure 10: Total wind curtailment by month, GB, and Scotland

Figure 10: Total wind curtailment by month, GB, and Scotland

Excess wind generation cannot be transmitted during periods of high wind outputs due to capacity constraints on the network. Storage technology solutions may be considered to mitigate these curtailments. Energy storage solutions for offshore applications are not fundamentally different to storage options for regular, onshore applications. They fall into the following categories: Mechanical, electrochemical, electrical, chemical, and thermal, and have been reviewed and assessed in many academic publications over the past decade. However, the offshore environment imposes constraints on technology deployment and operation, making some more suitable. Therefore, some references typically do not consider the specific challenges of the marine environment in their review of storage technologies. There are several potential ways in which wind curtailment [68], such as:

- Network reinforcements.
- Short duration storage.
- Long duration storage
- Demand side flexibility.
- Additional demand sources.
- Interconnector exports.

The combination of energy production from different offshore renewables in the same area could help to smooth the variability of the energy profile supplied to the power grid.

Wave and tidal energy converters have been developing for many decades and are in the advanced demonstration stage. Floating photovoltaic (PV) modules for converting solar energy is an emerging technology in the demonstration phase on inland basins [69]. More details on these technologies are reported in sub-sections 5.3.2, 5.3.1, and 5.3.3.

All the combinations mentioned above can be referred to as offshore hybrid systems [70]. Some research projects funded by the European Commission on this topic have been completed for years (ORECCA and MARINA PLATFORM), while others are ongoing (EU-SCORES). Two configurations are usually proposed: Sharing the platform (multi-purpose platform, multi-use platforms, energy island) or sharing the area (co-location), see the example in Figure 11 and Figure 12.

Figure 11: Conceptual design of the floating hybrid wind-wave platform system [71].

Figure 12: Co-location of floating wind and wave farm (Source Mocean Energy/Illustration – Wave Energy Scotland [72]).

The main advantages of offshore hybrid systems include:

- Better energy yield (increased production per occupied area),
- Improved production predictability,
- Smoothed output power,
- Shared network infrastructure and logistics,
- Potential sharing of foundations, platforms, moorings, and anchorages,
- Optimization of Operation & Maintenance (O&M) activities,
- Potential cost reduction,
- Environmental benefits,
- Enhanced social acceptability.
- Identified hybrid systems, potential barriers include:
 - Technological maturity (different maturity levels for different technologies, lengthy and varying timescales to reach commercialisation),
 - High costs (especially for some technologies and for the system overall due to the challenging environment),
 - Possible conflicts with other offshore and coastal activities,
 - Lack of adequate regulatory and consensual framework,
 - Concentration of environmental impacts,
 - Low social acceptability in general for all offshore infrastructures.
- Possible mitigations for these barriers include a common regulatory framework, defined maritime spatial planning, simplified authorisation processes, infrastructure development planning, and early stakeholder involvement.

5.3.1. Wave Energy: state of the art and market analysis

Wave energy converters (WECs) have been developing for many decades but have not yet reached the commercial stage. According to Mahdy, there are several challenges to be solved, i.e., the survival of WECs in extreme sea conditions, the best production in nominal resonant conditions, and the high variability of energy production [73]. There is still a lack of consensus on the design of the devices (see Figure 13), thus dispersing efforts and delaying cost reduction and standardisation. Very often, the design must be customised for the specific wave climate of the installation site.

Figure 13: An overview of WECs [73]

According to the Ocean Energy System, many WECs with different concepts reached 10-100 kW scale, with a projection for a MW full scale for a single device (i.e., TRITON devices from Oscilla Power under

test in the US and Archimede Waveswing from AWS Ocean Energy under test in the UK) [74] Concerning arrays, CorPower is preparing to deploy a 1.2 MW grid-connected array (four WECs) in the North of Portugal. The Mutriku Wave Power Plant, which has been operating on the coast of the Spanish Basque Country since 2011, must also be mentioned. The plant consists of 16 oscillating water column WECs with a total capacity of 296 kW.

Concerning the Mediterranean basin, the wave energy resource is well known to be significantly lower than in the North Sea and Ocean. However, many specialised devices are under study, among which the IWEC 250 kW point-absorber prototype was successfully deployed off the coast of Pantelleria Island in the South of Italy [74].

Cost assessment is difficult for this sector due to the number of different designs, the uncertainty about the effective performances of devices, the present costs and reduction path, and the investors' confidence. However, many studies have been carried out about the economics of WECs. Different organisations and researchers have put forward the target of the LCOE. According to a recently published review, "the common target cost of wave energy gradually converges to EUR 0.20/kWh by 2025 and EUR 0.15/kWh or GBP 150/MWh by 2030. The trend of the LCOE is decreasing, but it is still far away from the accepted target cost" [75].

Many studies have been carried out in the last decade assessing the co-location of wind and wave farms. Here are examples:

- A first review study confirms that "combined wave-wind resource is abundant, particularly in Europe and especially in Europe's North Atlantic sea basin. Wave and offshore wind technologies share many objectives [76]." Wave and offshore wind energies could share common and costly infrastructures and operational costs by sharing common O&M teams of facilities; use "WECs to shield the offshore wind park and reduce the wave height at the inner part".
- A study on wind and wave farm competitiveness: "First, offshore wind farms would obtain enlarged weather windows for O & M tasks, avoiding non-operational periods and the associated costs, while producing a smoother power output. Second, the inclusion of co-located WECs into wind farms could accelerate the development of wave energy technology, which may be expected to lead to reductions in the cost of wave energy based on the learning curve" [77].
- A study about an optimal control strategy for co-located wind and wave farms "to fulfil the operation and integration requirements demanded by power system operators [78]. The obtained results show that with adequate control strategies, it is possible to increase the electricity production of co-located wind-wave farms satisfying the frequency requirements of the network, even in adverse events, and to increase the total power".
- A study of the economics of the co-location of a floating wind farm with IEA 15MW reference wind turbines and a wave farm with CorPower WEC C4 device. The farms are of GW size at a site on the Northeastern shore of Portugal. The graph reported in Figure 14 shows the convenience of a wind-wave farm for the wave farm, which is standalone for a wave energy production capacity

factor lower than 40%. This value is already considered a high value for wave energy production [78].

Figure 14: LCOE of 1GW Wind-Wave Farm with increasing WEC Capacity Factor (CF) [79].

- An experimental investigation (tank test) aimed to assess the effect of WEC motion on wind turbine loads in a combined wind wave. “The results demonstrate that the horizontal force acting on the wind turbine substructure can be decreased by up to 40% subject to the WEC phase, amplitude and wave frequency” [80].

Artist’s impression of co-located wind and wave farm are reported in Figure 15.

Figure 15: Artist’s impression of co-located wind and wave farm.

5.3.2. Tidal Current Energy: state of the art and market analysis

The tidal current resource is related to the movement of ocean waters with tides. It generates a quite constant monodirectional flow that is highly predictable [83]. Many devices developed for converting tidal energy are like wind turbines installed underwater. These turbines are at a high 7-8 TRL. However, many other different designs for tidal devices are under study at different technological maturity stages [84], see Figure 16.

Figure 16: Tidal stream turbine design [84]

Tidal intensity is strongly dependent on latitude. Due to this feature, the viability of tidal current energy production in each area or site depends on the available resources, the costs, and the presence of infrastructure such as grid connections and installation facilities. i.e., in the Mediterranean Sea, studies agree to assess the higher tidal energy potential in the straits (Gibraltar, Dardanelly, Bonifacio, and Messina Straits) [85].

According to Ocean Energy Systems, many demonstrator projects are already operating MW size tidal turbines, such as the ones in MeyGen projects in Pentland Firth, Scotland [74]. The world's most powerful tidal device is the 2MW O2 by Orbital Marine Power, which hosts two 1 MW turbines. The demonstration is already at the array stage; for example, four tidal turbines are in the Nova Innovation Tidal Array at the Shetland Islands. The installation of many devices can also be done by sharing a platform. This is the case with the six turbines installed on the PLAT-I platform (total 420 kW) at Gran Passage, Canada.

Tidal energy devices are expected to operate and survive in a challenging environment for more than 20 years. At present, this means high investment and O&M costs and long-term reliability. Due to the resource's high spatial variability, different device designs, and the scarcity of historical data on devices and farms in operation, cost assessment presents a high uncertainty. According to an estimate by the Department of Energy, tidal energy costs \$130–280/MWh [86].

A complete and updated cost analysis can be found in the above cited Frazer-Nash study [84]. This study considers different development stages: current demo, first-of-a-kind (FOAK), and nth-of-a-kind (NOAK) (commercial stage). The study assesses, in 2022, an LCOE value for a large FOAK installation close to £260 ± 20/MWh. For 2050, in the scenarios "which aim to reflect projected TSE developments more closely", LCOE values range between £62/MWh & £80/MWh.

The integration of wind and tidal farms has already been investigated, i.e. concerning the integration of tidal turbines in the monopile foundation of the wind turbines [87]. The MeyGen demonstration project is ongoing in Pentland Firth, assessing the co-location approach. In 3.5 years, "12 MW wind farm with 20 MW tidal array gives a 70% increase in energy yield compared to the tidal array alone" [88].

5.3.3. Offshore floating photovoltaic: state of the art and market analysis

Various international and national sources show a revolution in the offshore renewable energy sector. As with wind technology, there is a growing trend towards utilising marine areas with floating installations for PV technology. These installations are already operational in several countries in freshwater, especially in lakes and reservoirs, as illustrated in Figure 17 [89].

Figure 17: Floating PV farm (73 kWp) On a lake in the Netherlands [90]

Offshore PV installations present greater challenges, especially regarding fouling and anchoring. Some demonstrative farms, even of significant size, have already been installed nearshore where the weather and marine conditions are milder than offshore, and access is simpler, as illustrated in Figure 18.

Figure 18: Nearshore floating PV farm (5 MWp) in Singapore [91].

Regarding floating PV installations in the open sea, challenges increase due to the impact of waves and wind. The technology for the platform is still under investigation. See artistic visualisation in Figure 19, and at present, the few cost studies show rather high values. In 2023, it announced that the 1 GW offshore solar power plant Shandong Dongying Kenli is under construction. The project is located 8 km off the coast of Laizhou Bay [92].

Figure 19: Offshore floating PV farm: artistic visualisation [93].

Interestingly, the floating photovoltaic sector, already demonstrated on lakes, presents significant advantages, including reduced water evaporation, decreased temperature of photovoltaic cells, and lower land rental costs. Integrating floating solar installations with offshore wind farms not only maximises energy generation synergistically but can also help offset seasonal production peaks, ensuring greater efficiency and resilience of offshore energy systems. However, it is important to consider that future photovoltaic installations intended for open sea must withstand adverse weather and climatic conditions and a particularly hostile marine environment for the metal components typically in a photovoltaic module. In selecting the photovoltaic module used for the analysis, the most efficient technology currently available on the market was chosen. It should be emphasised that this choice is closely linked to the power produced by the module based on its dimensions and does not consider the marine environment "hostile," which will require the adoption of a specially modified device to address increased thermal, mechanical, and chemical stresses when installed at sea.

Due to the low maturity stage, few studies are available about technology, operation, maintenance costs and LCOE for floating offshore PV farms. A DNV study reports that "the LCOE of offshore PV systems is currently estimated at around €354/MWh, but in the future, it should be close to that of ground-mounted solar parks, which for the Netherlands are estimated at €50/MWh in 2030 and €40/MWh in 2050. Their economic feasibility depends on the distance from the coast and the possibility of coupling to the grid connection of offshore wind" [94]. A study concerning three Italian offshore sites in the South of Italy with high solar resources assesses a more optimistic LCOE value of around 150€/MWh.

The hybrid energy system, which involves installing solar panels between offshore wind turbines, not only offers the possibility of generating energy during sunny days with lighter winds but also makes efficient use of shared marine space, see Figure 20. Some studies are already available about the combination of offshore wind and PV farms, i.e. enhancing the effectiveness of power smoothing or the survival and performance of the hybrid system under challenging environmental conditions [95] [96].

Figure 20: Co-location of offshore floating PV and wind farm: artistic visualisation [97].

5.3.4. Case studies

At the current stage of development, the considered technologies are at different maturity levels, and individual devices vary in size. The co-location hypothesis of parks with different devices seems to be the most flexible solution because it allows the design of parks with desired sizes to optimise the use of the space between turbines in offshore wind farms. The most promising combinations in European marine areas are mostly based on the available resources, site conditions, and infrastructure.

Wind energy is expected to become the leading technology in a short time. However, the potential integration of wave, tidal and solar technologies in a floating wind farm could facilitate their in-field demonstration and accelerate their maturity and commercialisation.

Some examples of techno-economic evaluations to confirm the expected benefits of using hybrid systems are reported in ANNEX 2. In particular, the results of the analysis of the following case studies are reported:

- Wind wave and solar (Sardinia - IT) potential production smoothing,
- Wind and solar (Ravenna -IT) increase of production in each area,
- Wind and solar (Sicily - IT) economic analysis for electrical infrastructure sharing,
- Wind and hydrogen production (Lazio - IT) techno-economic analysis.

5.4. Storage Systems

Floating offshore wind power holds immense potential for efficient energy production, thanks to the strong and stable winds in offshore environments. However, energy storage systems are crucial in fully harnessing this potential and integrating floating offshore wind into the grid. Here's how storage systems can advance the deployment of floating offshore wind:

Enhancing grid flexibility and stability: Energy storage solutions, such as those for frequency regulation and smart grid technologies, are essential in enhancing the grid's flexibility and accommodating the variable output of floating offshore wind farms. By storing excess energy during periods of low demand and releasing it during peak hours, storage systems help maintain a stable electricity supply and reduce strain on the grid.

Integrating renewable energy sources: Storage solutions can facilitate the integration of renewable energy sources, including floating offshore wind, into the grid. By storing surplus renewable energy and releasing it when needed, storage systems help mitigate the intermittent nature of renewables and ensure a consistent power supply. This enhances the grid's ability to accommodate the fluctuating generation from floating offshore wind farms.

Providing Backup Power and Resilience: Storage technologies play a crucial role in stabilising the grid by managing fluctuations in supply and demand, regulating frequency, and providing voltage support. This enhances grid reliability and minimises the risk of power outages or disruptions, essential for the reliable operation of floating offshore wind farms. Storage systems also serve as reliable backup power sources during emergencies or grid failures, ensuring uninterrupted electricity supply to critical services, businesses, and households. This enhances the grid's resilience and ensures operations continuity during adverse conditions, particularly important for floating offshore wind farms' remote and exposed nature.

Supporting demand response campaigns: Storage technology enables demand response programmes, allowing consumers to adjust their electricity usage to off-peak hours when energy prices are lower or renewable energy generation is abundant. This enhances grid flexibility and efficiency and reduces overall energy costs for consumers, supporting the integration of floating offshore wind into the grid.

5.4.1. Ongoing Research and Innovations

Ongoing research, such as at the Scaled Wind Farm Technology (SWiFT) facility, demonstrates that modulating wind turbine rotor rotation speed can provide grid load balancing and stability management. This load-balancing capability allows wind turbines to respond to fluctuations in power demand, supporting grid stability. Additionally, offshore wind projects like the North Sea Renewables Grid (NSRG) aim to decarbonise oil and gas operations by connecting floating offshore wind turbines to produce electricity and offset emissions.

Research conducted at the **Scaled Wind Farm Technology (SWiFT) facility** demonstrated that modulating the rotation speed of wind turbine rotors can provide load balancing and stability management on the grid [98].

- **Load balancing:** responding to sudden increases in power demand by sensing that more energy is being pulled from the plant than what is being produced. This response is triggered by detecting the reduction of the rotating kinetic energy of the generator's turbine. In other words, when the turbine slows down instead of remaining at its usual speed, the plant controls recognise that the plant needs to produce more power. This flexibility allows wind turbines to balance loads and support grid stability despite fluctuating energy demands. Additionally, wind turbines can offer valuable grid services and a new revenue source for wind plant operators.

- **Decarbonisation of Oil & Gas: an example of the** Cerulean Winds' plans to develop a North Sea Renewables Grid (NSRG) driven by floating offshore wind turbines that oil and gas platforms could connect to, aiming to produce multiple gigawatts of electricity and offset millions of tons of production emissions. The NSRG project involves multiple partners like NOV, Siemens Gamesa, Siemens Energy, DEME, and Worley, with an estimated investment cost of about £20 billion (\$25 billion). **(ScotWind INTOG):** designed in response to demand from government and industry to help achieve the targets of the North Sea Transition Sector Deal through decarbonising North Sea oil and gas operations, will also further stimulate innovation in Scotland's offshore wind sector, create additional supply chain opportunity, assist companies in entering the renewable energy market, and support net-zero ambitions [99] [100].

Energy storage for frequency regulation: Wind farms can play a crucial role in enhancing grid flexibility by using energy storage, providing frequency regulation, and offering black start capabilities. The integration of wind power into the grid is essential for maintaining a stable and reliable electricity supply, especially with the increasing share of variable renewable energy sources like wind and solar [101].

Energy storage solutions for offshore applications are not fundamentally different to storage options for regular, onshore applications. They fall into the following categories: Mechanical, electrochemical, electrical, chemical, and thermal, and have been reviewed and assessed in many academic publications over the past decade. However, the offshore environment imposes constraints on technology deployment and operation, making some more suitable. Therefore, the above references typically do not consider the specific challenges of the marine environment in their review of storage technologies.

The publication "A Review of marine renewable energy storage" [102] is used as the basis for the following review, with an addition from other sources.

Table 4: A review of marine renewable energy storage [102]

Energy Technology	Variation of technology	Description	Pros	Cons	Existing projects	TRL	
Mechanical/potential	Pumped Hydro Storage	Seawater PHS	The ocean is used as a lower reservoir	The classic version of PHS is the most mature and widespread storage technology.	Geological constraints: Having a high upper reservoir near the shore	Okinawa, Japan	
		Subsea PHS	Compressing water (and sometimes air) in a vessel located at the seabed.	Can be used to anchor floating offshore wind turbines.	Requires favourable seabed conditions.	StEnSea; DODGES, Subhydro Storage,	
		Low water head PHS	Making use of small height differences.	Can be done where altitude difference is not available.	Low water head making it more difficult to capture	Energy island concept. Tidal power stations.	
	Subterranean PHS	Use of an underground reservoir instead of a high altitude one.	No need for high hills	Digging an underground cave can be highly expensive			
	Compressed Air Energy Storage (CAES)	Traditional CAES	Air is compressed into a tank/reservoir in the charging phase and expanded during the discharge. The discharge phase requires heating the air with fossil fuels.	Long life cycle; Large storage capacity; maturity	Running on fossil fuels; Low energy density; Low efficiency (thermal energy wasted)	Huntorf 321MW McIntosh 110MW	Commercialisation
		2 nd Generation CAES	Same as above, but the fuel runs a turbine generating heat and electricity.	Higher efficiency than 1 st generation	Wasted thermal energy	CAES-AI, CAES-IC	R&D
		Adiabatic CAES	Same as traditional, but no fossil fuel: the thermal energy from compression is recovered and used for expansion.	High efficiency No fossil fuels	Low thermal losses are needed to ensure efficiency.	TICC-500 500kW ALACAES 1MWh AA-CAES 10MW	Demonstration & Deployment
Isothermal CAES		It is the same as Adiabatic but with two isothermal levels: cold from expanded air cools down incoming airflow, and heat from compressed air warms air before expansion.	Very high theoretical efficiency. No high temperature is required.	It is a more complex system. It is difficult to remain isothermal in practice.	ICAES 1.65MW GCAES 2MW	Demonstration & Deployment	

D3.2: Analysis of technological barriers and enablers of

floating offshore wind

LAES	More compression stages with heat exchange lead to liquefying air (or nitrogen)	Much higher energy density	Highly complex, including more thermal losses	Highview Power 350kW and another 5MW/15MWh	Demonstration & Deployment
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The latest developments are bringing various technologies closer to integration into electrical grids. These include electrochemical batteries (such as flow batteries, lithium-ion, sodium-ion, etc.), electromechanical systems (including compressed CAES or liquid LAES air, compressed carbon dioxide, flywheels, gravity storage, etc.), pumped storage hydropower, hydrogen storage and supercapacitors. Additionally, other technologies are less widely considered, such as thermal storage and superconducting magnetic energy.

Grid requirements will vary depending on the characteristics of each technology used within the power grid. Some technologies, like batteries, react quickly but lack significant storage capacity, while others react slowly yet offer substantial energy storage, such as storage facilities. From the grid's perspective, there are three categories of energy storage, with additional storage solutions falling in between these extremes [103].

- Short duration: used to balance grid responses within seconds or minutes.
- Medium duration: used for intraday power balance, lasting from hours to days.
- Long duration: accommodating large quantities of energy for interseason power storage.

Despite the growth in battery storage, limitations still exist regarding storage capacity, rendering it unsuitable for certain applications. For instance, large-scale, long-term storage necessary for seasonal backup or energy security reserves in the absence of fossil fuels demands alternative technology [104].

Short-term storage solutions for grid balancing require swift reaction times rather than extensive storage capacity. In contrast, medium- and long-term storage solutions prioritise storage capacity suitable for intraday or intersessional use over rapid response times.

Research efforts are focused on exploring novel storage technologies beyond traditional batteries. These include pumped hydro storage, compressed air energy storage, thermal energy storage, and hydrogen storage. Each of these solutions offers unique advantages and applications for grid capacity enhancement. Pumped hydro storage, for example, leverages elevation differences to store and release energy, while hydrogen storage enables long-term energy storage and compatibility with various energy sources.

Combined with hydrogen production. Innovations in hydrogen storage methods aim to improve efficiency, scalability, and safety for integrating hydrogen into grid systems. These advancements hold promise for supporting sustainable energy initiatives in the future. These are underway to address critical challenges and expand grid capacity. The process of combining hydrogen production with offshore wind energy is known as Power-To-Gas. This involves storing energy through the production of hydrogen, which can then be used as a fuel or stored for later use. Three main configurations can be analysed for this approach: (1)-Onshore hydrogen Production: The hydrogen plant is located onshore; (2)- offshore centralised hydrogen production: The hydrogen plant is located on an offshore platform; and (3)- offshore decentralised hydrogen production: A hydrogen plant is integrated into each offshore turbine platform.

In the last two options, offshore wind energy production is generally fully dedicated to green hydrogen production, as transporting electricity and hydrogen to shore is very expensive. Studies suggest that hydrogen pipelines may be cheaper than wind energy export cables, making hybrid systems with offshore hydrogen production a viable option.

To address the variability of wind energy production, the exploitation of other offshore renewable resources can be considered, such as Wave energy- which generally follows the variability of wind resources with a delayed and smoother profile; Tidal energy with a more predictable variation daily; and Solar energy with higher production in the summer, while wind and waves are typically higher in the winter.

By combining these diverse renewable sources, stakeholders can better manage the variability of energy supply and support the transition to a more sustainable energy future.

6. CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, floating offshore wind technology advancements rely on addressing critical areas across various domains. Key technological enablers, such as platform design and stability, mooring and anchoring systems, wind turbine performance, and operation and maintenance, are crucial for optimising floating offshore wind farms' efficiency, sustainability, and cost-effectiveness.

Efforts such as the LIFES50+, ECO2FOW, and FLOTANT projects demonstrate ongoing research to overcome technical challenges, enhance environmental considerations, and improve overall system performance. These initiatives showcase the industry's commitment to innovation and sustainability [51] [105].

Financial barriers pose a significant challenge to the deployment of floating wind projects. To overcome these hurdles, measures such as public funding and support, successful pilot demonstrations, collaborative risk-sharing ventures, and the establishment of supportive regulatory frameworks are crucial for attracting private investment and fostering confidence among stakeholders.

Addressing environmental impacts is equally vital for the responsible development of floating offshore wind farms. Thorough environmental impact assessments, careful site selection, monitoring and adaptive management strategies, stakeholder engagement, and adherence to best practices and guidelines are essential in mitigating potential ecosystem risks.

Regulatory and permitting challenges can be addressed through concerted efforts among policymakers, regulators, and industry stakeholders. Developing supportive regulatory frameworks, streamlining permitting processes, enhancing stakeholder engagement, and fostering collaboration are key strategies to create a conducive environment for successfully deploying floating wind projects.

In summary, the future of floating offshore wind hinges on a holistic approach that integrates technological innovation, financial strategies, environmental stewardship, and effective regulatory frameworks. By addressing these key themes, the industry can pave the way for the widespread adoption of this renewable energy source, contributing to a more sustainable and resilient energy future.

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8. ANNEX

8.1. Wind wave and solar (Sardinia - IT) potential production smoothing

In this case, three distinct technologies were specifically examined:

- A wind turbine with a nominal power of 15 MW (IEA 15-240-RWT [106]),
- A photovoltaic module with a nominal power of 400 W (SUNPOWER MAXEON [107]),
- A Wave Energy Converter (WEC) with a nominal power of 4500 W (WaveSAX [108]).

The normalisation of generated powers was essential for comparing the production variability of each device around the average value calculated over a specific period—in this case, one year. This was necessary due to the significant differences in nominal power among the considered technologies.

A typical offshore meteorological year (TMY) was utilised to assess the resource variability at the site. This year comprised of months from different years that provided the best description of the overall behaviour of the resource at the identified location over a long-period dataset (10 years) [109]. Specifically, the site in Sardinia shows significant promise for wind conditions compared to other Italian locations. Additionally, the solar irradiance at this site is particularly strong due to its latitude. When analysing the variability among these different technologies, the focus was solely on the power generated by individual devices to calculate the normalised value. This analysis did not consider factors typical of a farm setup, such as inverter losses, wake losses, etc. This is because this analysis is aimed at pre-sizing the hybrid system, which means it does not require the system to be already dimensioned. To compare the power generated by each technology within a hypothetical offshore hybrid system, the hourly generated power at each time instant ($P_{Device}^{Gen.}(t)$) was normalised over the maximum power value generated by each considered device during the TMY (P_{Device}^{Max}). Finally, the normalised hourly power $P_{Device}^{Norm.}(t)$ for each device in each hour was calculated using the following expression:

$$P_{Device}^{Norm.}(t) = \frac{P_{Device}^{Gen.}(t)}{P_{Device}^{Max}}$$

With $t = 1 \div 8760$, specific time instant, expressed in an hour, in the TMY.

Subsequently, the normalised production curve of the hybrid system, incorporating the three technologies above, was computed considering its value at each time instant, calculated with the following expression:

$$P_{Hybrid\ System}^{Norm.}(t) = \frac{[c_{PV} \cdot P_{PV}^{Norm.}(t) + c_{WIND} \cdot P_{WIND}^{Norm.}(t) + c_{WEC} \cdot P_{WEC}^{Norm.}(t)]}{P_{Hybrid\ System}^{Max}}$$

Utilising c_{Device} as a specific coefficient permits the evaluation of the normalised power generated from the hybrid system while freely adjusting the size of each device. In this preliminary analysis, a value of 1 was allocated to each device, representing a scenario where the same size was considered for every technology. This approach enables a flexible comparison of the power outputs from different

configurations of the hybrid system, accommodating varying sizes of individual devices. The figure below illustrates the specific trend of normalised power generated by each device over the TMY. This allows for highlighting the different seasonal production patterns from each technology. Specifically, the wind turbine and the WEC exhibit peak production during winter and lower values during summer. In contrast, the normalised photovoltaic module power trend in red demonstrates the opposite pattern.

Figure 21: Specific trend of normalised power generated by each device over the TMY.

In analogy with what has just been shown for each device, the graph illustrating the trend of normalised power generated by the hybrid system over the TMY is provided in Figure 22, indicating a relatively

stable yearly pattern. However, it also reveals higher values during the early and late periods of the year, coinciding with the production peaks observed from both the WEC and offshore wind turbines.

Figure 22: Trend of normalised power generated by the hybrid system over the TMY.

To enhance the understanding of the variability in normalised power generated by the hybrid system, its trend is highlighted over four weeks, representing four different seasons within the TMY.

Figure 23: The trend of the normalised power generated by the hybrid system is one week during each of the four seasons during the TMY.

Figure 23 clearly illustrates the central power peak generated by the hybrid system, which is attributed to the photovoltaic module. This is particularly evident on D5 and D6 of the winter week when there appears to be reduced power generation from the WEC and the offshore wind turbine.

The provided summer week highlights the photovoltaic module's importance in shaping the hybrid system's production profile. Here, each day shows a distinct peak in production during the midday hours. Lastly, it is important to note that the normalised power trend in the considered spring week does not display any periods of zero generation. This underscores the significance of diversifying renewable sources to reduce the unpredictability of production and achieve a more consistent power curve. The contribution from the wind turbine is notably evident during winter, spring, and autumn, displaying consistently high-power values even during nighttime hours (near the black vertical lines on the Figure 23). On the other hand, the importance of the WEC's contribution, along with that of the wind turbine, is underscored by its slow power variation compared to the photovoltaic module. This notably reduces the typical ramp-up and ramp-down periods observed with the photovoltaic module, especially during the early and late hours of the day. Several examples of these patterns are visible in D3 and D4 of the autumn week and D2 of the winter week, along with other instances throughout the remaining weeks.

To assess the smoothing achieved by the hybrid plant's generation compared to each technology's power output, the Relative Mean Deviation (RMD) was calculated. This metric provides a relative measure of data dispersion, expressing the standard deviation as a percentage of the mean using the following formulas:

$$P_{Device}^{Average} = \frac{\sum_{k=1}^N P_{Device}^{Norm.}(t)}{N}$$

With k : The number of intervals in the dataset varies from 1 to N .

$$RMD = \frac{\sqrt{\sum_{k=1}^N [P_{Device}^{Norm.}(t) - P_{Device}^{Average}]^2}}{P_{Device}^{Average}} \quad [\%]$$

The results obtained from the analysis are listed in the table below and divided by type of technology.

	Mean Value [-]	RMD [%]
Hybrid System	0.24	67%
Wind Turbine	0.40	88%
PV Module	0.18	124%
WEC	0.14	96%

The comparison of the results shows that the production variability is significantly diminished by integrating the three examined technologies into a hybrid system. However, it is important to note that despite this decrease in variability, the overall average power generated by the hybrid system is lower than that of the standalone wind farm. This can primarily be attributed to the relatively low power output of the wave motion conversion device, a consequence of the site's "mild state" wave climate. Furthermore, the cyclical nature of day and night, resulting in prolonged periods of

photovoltaic inactivity, also contributes to this device's reduced average normalised power output. Consequently, these factors collectively lead to a diminished average normalised power value for the entire hybrid system.

8.2. Wind and solar (Ravenna -IT) increase of production in a given area

An offshore wind farm was conceptualised with rows spaced 10 diameters apart in the prevailing wind direction and 7 diameters apart orthogonal to that [110]. The detailed spatial arrangement of the turbines and the platforms hosting the photovoltaic modules is illustrated in the figure below.

Figure 24: Layout of the conceptual offshore Hybrid System: photovoltaic platforms (Grey) + Wind turbines (Red).

The sea area off Ravenna, and more broadly across Emilia-Romagna, features shallow depths suitable for primarily fixed foundation wind farms, indicating a limited wind potential. This is underscored by the lower capacity factor observed when simulating an offshore wind farm installation in this region.

Considering a park totalling approximately 1 GW, comprised of 67 turbines each generating 15 MW (IEA 15-240-RWT [106]), with a hub height of 150 m above sea level, an analysis using a 10-year dataset (2010-2019) of wind values at this height from the AEOLIAN [111] The new Italian Wind Atlas by RSE yields a Capacity Factor of 21.64, with an average wind speed at the hub of 5.81 m/s.

The possibility of installing a floating photovoltaic park alongside it has been explored to enhance renewable energy production from the sea area occupied by the offshore wind farm. Due to the considerably lower height of the photovoltaic panel structures compared to the hub height of the turbines and considering the substantial distance between each row of turbines, it is anticipated that there will be minimal wake effect. As a result, no "negative" interactions, such as shading and interference, are expected between the two installations.

When considering an offshore photovoltaic park of equal size, consisting of 2,512,500 modules, each producing 400 W (SUNPOWER MAXEON [107]), and utilising the MERIDA HRES dataset for irradiance,

temperature, and wind speed values at the height of the photovoltaic modules to calculate the generated power, a capacity factor of 12.30 is obtained. Despite the lower capacity factor obtained compared to that of the offshore wind farm, it is worth noting that this photovoltaic park was located within the rows of turbines that make up the wind farm [112]. As a result, the overall specific production from the area of sea occupied consists of the combined production from both the wind farm and the photovoltaic park. The offshore wind farm occupies a total area of 225 km². When considering only the wind farm, the specific production is 8468 MWh/km². However, with the addition of the hybrid system (photovoltaic and offshore wind), the specific production increases to 13281 MWh/km². This represents a substantial increase of approximately 157% in the annual energy generated from the same area of sea.

The following two figures (Figure 25 - Figure 26) display the power generation patterns of the offshore wind and photovoltaic park at the selected site, focusing on winter and summer periods. A distinct complementarity in production between the two technologies is evident. The photovoltaic system, depicted by the red line, shows peaks of production concentrated during the summer months and reduced output in winter. In contrast, the wind power, represented by the blue curve, demonstrates production peaks during winter and lower levels during summer.

Figure 25 – Trend of winter power generation from the offshore wind and photovoltaic park.

Figure 26 - Trend of summer power generation from the offshore wind and photovoltaic park.

This underscores not only the potential to enhance renewable energy yield from the same marine area but also the ability to achieve more consistent seasonal power profiles compared to those resulting from the separate installation of each technology.

8.3. Wind and solar (Sicily - IT) economic analysis for electrical infrastructure sharing

The primary parameter for the economic evaluation is the Levelised Cost of Energy (LCOE). This parameter, particularly in the simplified version employed here, depends on the capital costs (CAPEX), operational costs (OPEX), average annual electricity production delivered to the grid, expressed as a percentage of the Capacity Factor (CF), the project's useful life, and the discount rate, represented by the Weighted Average Cost of Capital (WACC).

Five types of installations were considered and compared: a standalone offshore floating wind farm, an integrated offshore floating wind farm, a standalone offshore floating solar PV farm, an integrated offshore PV farm, and a hybrid facility that integrates wind and solar power generation. The conceptual layout, as depicted in Figure 24, of the turbines and photovoltaic modules in the wind farm was used for analysis. In the case of the hybrid setup, it is assumed that the PV system can deliver energy through the wind farm's export cable. This means that the costs associated with the electrical infrastructure of the PV system are not included in the expenses of the integrated facility. However, there are instances when the hybrid system's energy production exceeds the cable's capacity, leading to wind power curtailment. For both technologies, a useful life of 30 years was assumed. For whatever concern, CAPEX and OPEX values for the wind farm are derived from a previously developed model, while those for the offshore floating PV system are estimated based on limited literature data [113] [114] [115]. For the assessment of the total power generated by the offshore hybrid system (photovoltaic and wind), the shadow cast by the turbines on the photovoltaic modules was evaluated, as depicted in the Figure 27.

Figure 27 - Shadows cast by the turbines obscure the photovoltaic modules installed within the wind farm.

To calculate the shading, the sun's height at the site was considered every moment throughout the year (Figure 28). Geometrically calculating the minimum and maximum shading angles as depicted in Figure 27, the overall reduction in power generated by the photovoltaic array was assessed. A conservative approach was taken for the shading assessment, considering the area shaded by the entire disc where the wind turbine blades rotate. Additionally, it was assumed that the sun's height always caused shadows on the photovoltaic modules to be present for ease of calculation and a

conservative estimate. However, because of the Earth's rotation and site orientation, it is not guaranteed that the minimum distance between the photovoltaic platform and the turbine platform occurs when the sun is at its lowest point in the sky.

Figure 28 - Solar Paths are considered Sites in the Sicily Channel.

In the hypothetical case study of a park installed in the Sicily Channel, a turbine mounted on a semi-submersible platform with a hub height of 150 m and a rotor diameter of 242 m was considered. A floating structure for the photovoltaic park with a height of 2 m was also considered. Simple geometric calculations yielded a minimum shading angle (ϑ_{MIN}) of 12.53° and a maximum (ϑ_{MAX}) of 15.53° .

As shown in Figure 24, the park includes 16 turbines spaced at a minimum distance of 5 diameters from the photovoltaic platform. The maximum shadow cast by the turbines covers 13% of the total area of the photovoltaic platform. To calculate the power reduction due to shading, the 13% factor was applied to the power generated at every moment when the sun's height was lower than the maximum angle (a conservative approach).

The graph below (Figure 29) shows the trends in total power generated by the offshore photovoltaic park, indicated in red, and the power lost due to shading from the presence of wind turbines in the hybrid system. The graph also displays the energy obtained annually by summing the powers calculated for each moment over 8760 hours.

Figure 29 – Annual power generation from the offshore photovoltaic park (Red) and power loss due to shading of the modules caused by the shadow cast by the turbines (Green).

It is important to highlight that, with turbines in the park and a conservative approach in the calculations, there is an annual loss of 7 GWh. This loss represents just 0.57% of the park's annual generation of 1288 GWh, demonstrating the effectiveness and practicality of this hybrid solution.

Regarding OPEX, sufficient data are not yet available to confidently define the value to be attributed, especially for offshore photovoltaic systems. Therefore, a range of values has been considered, ranging from 0.5%, close to that for onshore installations, to 3%. Similarly, three cases have been considered for the WACC of hybrid systems with a minimum value of 5% up to a maximum of 9%. Finally, the LCOE of the hybrid system has been calculated as the weighted average of the specific LCOEs calculated for each technology on the energy produced and thus transmitted by each of them (wind and photovoltaic).

The results obtained are shown in the graph below (Figure 30), where the case with the minimum value of photovoltaic OPEX and minimum hybrid System WACC has been labelled "Best Case," the one with OPEX of 1.75% and WACC equal to 7% as "Medium Case," and the case with OPEX of 3% and WACC of 9% as "Worst Case."

Figure 30 - Results of an economic analysis for the case study of a hybrid system considered installed in the Sicily Channel.

From the values reported in Figure 30, the significance of sharing the electrical infrastructure between the wind and photovoltaic installations to reduce the latter's LCOE is evident. This is especially noticeable in all the cases illustrated; for instance, in the Best Case, there is a reduction in LCOE of approximately 22.6% when excluding the offshore photovoltaic park's CAPEX from the export electrical infrastructure cost calculation. Similarly, this reduction is 23% in the Medium Case and 22.9% in the Worst Case.

Despite the considerable disparity in the LCOE values of offshore photovoltaic systems, both integrated and standalone, the advantage of co-locating with a wind farm to create a hybrid system is emphasised by the substantial cost reduction. For instance, when considering the LCOE values of the "PV INTEGRATED" shown in Figure 30, the ratio between the Worst Case (205 €/MWh) and the Best Case (113 €/MWh) is 181%. However, due to the substantial power generation capacity of the offshore wind farm, the LCOE of the hybrid system in the worst-case scenario (155 €/MWh) is only 145% of that obtained in the best-case scenario (107 €/MWh).

It is important to note that the LCOE of the integrated wind system is consistently higher than that of the stand-alone case. This is due to the need for curtailment, which occurs when the transmission cable to the shore becomes saturated. Additionally, despite the decrease in production and thus of energy transmission between stand-alone and integrated photovoltaics, as shown in the shading analysis, there is a significant reduction in the LCOE values. This reduction is attributed to the savings gained from sharing the export infrastructure of the wind farm, as mentioned earlier.

8.4. Wind and hydrogen production (Lazio - IT) techno-economic analysis

In this case study, the investigation centred on the feasibility of placing an electrolyser onshore near the transformer substation of a 1 GW offshore wind farm, a capacity equivalent to those analysed in prior case studies. The study assessed hydrogen production cost through electrolysis, utilising a polymer membrane electrolyser (PEM). Three distinct scenarios for hydrogen production were outlined, with variations in production efficiency ranging between 65% and 75%, aligning with values identified by the International Energy Agency (IEA) [116]. Alongside, the size of the electrolyser was adjusted, ranging from a minimum of 250 MW—approximately 25% of the considered offshore wind farm's capacity—to a maximum capacity of 100%. Within each of the three scenarios, the study evaluated the CAPEX of the electrolyser, ranging from 500 to 1000 €/kW. Additionally, customised parameters were set for the equivalent production hours of the electrolyser, ranging from a minimum of 3000 hours per year to a maximum of 5000 hours. It is emphasised that if the electrolyser were grid-connected, it could operate for 8760 hours per year, accounting for maintenance downtime.

The subsequent graph illustrates the variation of the Levelized Cost of Hydrogen (LCOH) concerning the input energy price at the electrolyser. Notably, when sourced from renewable sources, such as offshore wind, the resulting hydrogen is classified as "green".

Figure 31: LCOH variation with respect to the cost of the energy supplying the electrolyser in three different cases.

The table below includes all the bibliographic references for the LCOE of each represented renewable technology projected to 2030.

Name	Unit of Measure	Min Value	Max Value	Reference
Floating offshore wind				
WINDEUROPE	€/MWh	53	76	https://windeurope.org/wp-content/uploads/files/policy/position-papers/20211202-WindEurope-Scaling-up-Floating-Offshore-Wind-towards-competitiveness.pdf
IRENA	USD/MWh	50	90	https://www.irena.org/-/media/Files/IRENA/Agency/Publication/2019/Oct/IRENA_Future_of_wind_2019.pdf
SERRI et al.	€/MWh	70	156	Serri, Laura & Colle, Lisa & Vitali, Bruno & Bonomi, Tullia. (2020). Floating Offshore Wind Farms in Italy beyond 2030 and 2060: Preliminary Results of a Techno-Economic Assessment. Applied Sciences. 10. 8899. 10.3390/app10248899.
PV Utility Scale				
IRENA	USD 2018/MWh	20	80	https://www.irena.org/-/media/Files/IRENA/Agency/Publication/2019/Nov/IRENA_Future_of_Solar_PV_2019.pdf
ETIP The European Technology and Innovation platform for photovoltaics	€/MWh (Rome)	Ca. 17	Ca. 28	Low-cost PV - The Key for Sustainable Future Energy System https://etip-pv.eu/publications/etip-pv-publications/
ONSHORE WIND				
IRENA	USD/MWh	30	50	https://www.irena.org/-/media/Files/IRENA/Agency/Publication/2019/Oct/IRENA_Future_of_wind_2019_summ_EN.pdf?la=en&hash=D07089441987EBABC7F4BED63B62C83820C18724

WEC				
GUO et al.	€/MWh	113	226	Guo C, Sheng W, De Silva DG, Aggidis G. A Review of the Levelized Cost of Wave Energy Based on a Techno-Economic Model. <i>Energies</i> . 2023; 16(5):2144. https://doi.org/10.3390/en16052144
Strategic Energy Technology (SET) Plan In EU	€/MWh	150		https://energy.ec.europa.eu/topics/renewable-energy/offshore-renewable-energy_en
OCEAN ENERGY EUROPE	€/MWh (Depends on cumulative MWs installed)	81	168	https://www.oceanenergy-europe.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/10/OEE_2030_Ocean_Energy_Vision.pdf
Strategic Energy Technology (SET) Plan In EU	€/MWh	100		https://energy.ec.europa.eu/topics/renewable-energy/offshore-renewable-energy_en
TIDAL				
OCEAN ENERGY EUROPE	€/MWh (Depends on cumulative MWs installed)	94	181	https://www.oceanenergy-europe.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/10/OEE_2030_Ocean_Energy_Vision.pdf
Bottom Fixed Offshore Wind				
Aegir, NREL	€/MWh	ca. 38	ca. 53	https://www.nrel.gov/wind/assets/pdfs/engineering-wkshp2022-1-1-jensen.pdf

The graph highlights the significance of the input energy cost to the electrolyser in the three considered scenarios. Particularly, it is underscored that if renewable energy is used to produce green hydrogen, the initial price to consider for the input energy depends heavily on the Levelized Cost of Electricity (LCOE) of these technologies, which is strongly influenced by the local meteorological conditions of their installation. In the graph, differently coloured rectangles represent LCOE ranges identified in various studies and case studies for each technology by 2030. This indicates that by powering the electrolyser with renewable energy from different sources, the resulting LCOH varies across a wide range of values. Finally, various connection options were considered, which can vary depending on the opening of the switches, as indicated in black in the following Figure 32.

Figure 32: Connection options considered with two configurations

The electrolyser was considered to be installed in two different configurations:

1. **Stand Alone:** The electrolyser is solely connected to the offshore wind farm for power supply. This refers to the scenario where the switch depicted in Figure 32 and marked in black is in the open position.
2. **Grid Connected:** Initially, the wind farm powered the electrolyser up to predetermined amounts of energy. Once the target annual equivalent hours of hydrogen production for the electrolyser were defined, additional electricity was sourced from the grid. Despite a notable increase in hydrogen production due to achieving high equivalent hours values, the hydrogen obtained using grid electricity was considered non-green.

To calculate the LCOH, they used the following simplified expression, akin to other studies conducted by the authors [], where, apart from CAPEX and OPEX, they accounted for the cost of energy divided between the grid and the wind farm as highlighted in the following expression:

$$\text{Simple LCOH} = \frac{\text{CAPEX} \cdot \text{CRF} + \text{OPEX} + C_{\text{WindEnergy}} + C_{\text{GridEnergy}}}{H_2 \text{ Produced}}$$

The denominator contains the total amount of hydrogen produced by the selected electrolyser, which varies based on the hydrogen production efficiency, equivalent production hours, and the size of the electrolyser itself. To determine the quantity of green hydrogen produced, a ratio was established between the energy provided as input from the wind farm and that from the grid to the total hydrogen produced. Notably, this preliminary analysis did not consider the transportation or transformation system of the hydrogen produced downstream of the electrolyser. Thus, the identified LCOH characterises the pure generation aspect.

For the wind farm situated in Lazio, the LCOE was calculated to be 117.1 €/MWh [110]. Considering the Grid Connected setup, where it is projected that 10% of the net energy generated by the wind farm is earmarked for H2 production, and in addition to this allocation, the energy "curtailed" due to curtailment is fully supplied to the electrolyser, with a total variable value across 3 scenarios ranging from a minimum of 5% of the NAEP to a maximum of 15%. This analysis also factors in the costs associated with purchasing these energies as follows:

- Cost of energy dedicated to hydrogen production:
 - o Case A: 250 €/MWh
 - o Case B: 185 €/MWh
 - o Case C: 117.1 €/MWh
- Cost of Curtailment corresponding to the LCOE of the wind farm in each case
- Cost of energy purchased from the grid: 70 €/MWh.

All the parameters used in the analysis and the numerical results obtained have been entered into the table below.

PARAMETER	UNIT OF MEASURE	CASE A	CASE B	CASE C
LCoE	€/MWh	117.1		
Net Annual Energy Production (NAEP)	GWh	2502.4		
% of NAEP supplying the Ely	%	10		
Cost of NAEP supplying the Ely	€/MWh	250	185	117
Grid annual average energy Price	€/MWh	70		
% of NAEP representing the curtailment	%	5	10	15
Cost of Curtailment for H2	€/MWh	117.1		
Production efficiency of Hydrogen	%	65	70	75
Electrolyser's size	MW	250	500	1000
Full load hour of production of Hydrogen	h	3000	4000	5000

CAPEX Ely	€/kW	500		
% CAPEX to substitute Stacks	% capexel	11		
OPEX Ely	%CAPEXtot	3.5		
Wind Farm WACC	%	5		
Electrolyser Grid Connected	Boolean	True		
Total Input Energy from Grid	GWh	374.6	1499.5	4374.4
Total Input Energy from Wind Farm	GWh	375.4	500.5	625.6
RESULTS				
H2 Annual production	KTon	14.6	42	112.5
GreenH2 Annual Production	kTon	7.3	10.5	14.1
LCOH	€/kg	8.02	4.96	3.87

The results underscore the importance of low-cost renewable energy as input for the electrolyser. Thus, developing technologies such as offshore wind, which can reliably provide green energy for extended periods throughout the year, becomes particularly crucial. Specifically, the potential to combine multiple renewable energies in hybrid renewable systems (as illustrated in the specific case study) would lead to an increased availability of the necessary renewable energy for producing green hydrogen. It is crucial to highlight the significance of the Full Load Hour parameter in determining the LCOH. To achieve substantial hydrogen production, having a high number of Full Load Hours is essential. Moreover, there is a noteworthy opportunity to offset curtailments in wind farms by directing the excess energy, which would otherwise not be utilised by the grid, to the electrolyser. In this case study, the cost for this excess energy was assumed to be equal to the LCOE of the Wind Farm. However, in a future where electricity generation will predominantly rely on renewable technologies, subject to the inherent fluctuations in power output, the current system of compensating for curtailments may no longer suffice. Therefore, innovative solutions must be devised to ensure that these renewable energy installations do not suffer from penalties due to grid saturation. The production of hydrogen and the potential to integrate renewable parks with storage systems will significantly enhance the resilience of the entire energy system. This, in turn, will help reduce losses of generated energy, particularly renewable ones.